

Studies on the Balkan Lepidoptera I

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Abstract: New and interesting records of Balkan Lepidoptera are detailed. One genus and three species are new for the Balkan fauna, one of them, *Chondrosoma fiduciaria* Anker, 1854, is a species from Annex II of the EEC 92/43 Habitat Directive. Two other species and one subspecies are proven to be a part of the Balkan fauna. The majority of the species are from the informal group “Macrolepidoptera”, but we include as well as some representatives of the informal group “Microlepidoptera”. Seven genera and 33 species and one subspecies are new for Albania, and 20 species are reported for the second time. For Montenegro, three genera and 12 species are new. Three species are new for the Republic of North Macedonia, and the second locality is reported for three other species. The genus *Sympistis* and nine species are new and five species are reported for the second time for Serbia. One genus and three species are new to Bulgaria and five are reported for the second time. One genus and two species are new for Bosnia and Herzegovina. One genus and three species are new for Greece. For many other species, third localities are reported for certain countries. For other species we report the highest or lowest altitude localities and southernmost/easternmost points of their range so far known. Data for some other interesting species from these countries are also presented, including new localities for species with poorly known distribution in the Balkan Peninsula and Balkan countries. Many data originate from non-explored areas in certain countries, from where we have a lack of information. Altogether, data for 442 species of Lepidoptera from more than 120 localities are presented here, and selected habitats, specimens, and their genitalia are illustrated in 359 figures.

Keywords: Balkan countries, butterflies, Europe, faunistics, moths

Introduction

The Balkan countries have been rather patchily explored for Lepidoptera, especially for nocturnal species, and there are many species with insufficiently clear distribution, especially concerning recently described taxa. Some data have been erroneously reported through neglect of examination of the genitalia. It becomes more difficult to find new taxa for countries such as Bulgaria, North Macedonia, and Greece, and now even for Albania where, over the last eight years, the present authors have conducted intensive research (except for the years 2020 and 2021 during the pandemic). This country was visited regularly each year, three to five times, in different seasons and for different durations. After 2022, we collected mostly in fresh localities in search of new data; if we collected in previously visited localities, we did it in different seasons. However, some species that are

common in the neighbouring countries species had not yet been found in Albania, for example *Herminia tarsipennalis* Treitschke, 1835, *Herminia tarsicrinalis* (Knoch, 1782), *Colobochyla salicalis* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Autographa pulchrina* (Haworth, 1809), *Actinotia polyodon* (Clerck, 1759), *Amphipoea oculea* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Eupsilia transversa* (Hufnagel, 1766), *Enargia paleacea* (Esper, [1788]), *Tholera cespitis* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Polia bombycina* (Hufnagel, 1766), and *Lacanobia suasa* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775). From them, only *Herminia tarsipennalis*, *Herminia tarsicrinalis*, and *Tholera cespitis* were found new for Albania and reported in this article.

The nocturnal Lepidoptera fauna of the Republic of North Macedonia is better explored, but mostly by foreigners, and the majority of the data are from only a few localities. At the same time, for large areas of the country, there are practically no records. Finding

new species for that country is most likely to be among difficult groups and large genera, where examination of genitalia is necessary. Recording new localities of species already reported from a single locality is, however, relatively easy. Almost the same situation pertains in Serbia, where over the last eleven years the present authors have published separately or together more than 63 Macrolepidoptera species new for that country, including one species new for science. In Montenegro the Durmitor National Park, the Adriatic coast, and other tourist areas are relatively well-explored, but there is a lack of data from other parts of that country. The data for the late-autumn and the early-spring species for this country are scarce. From Bulgaria we here present data from some areas as Sakar, Golo Bardo Mt, Danubian Plain, etc., from where we had a lack of information or only scarce data. In Serbia we continued to explore mountain areas in the eastern part of the country and Rtanj Mt, where the plant *Artemisia alba* Turra is well represented (Habitat type: Mountain petrophytic steppes 02E1. Relationships with habitat classifications: EUNIS: E1.21 Helleno-Balkan [*Satureja montana*] steppes; PAL. CLASS.: 34.311 Helleno-Balkan savory steppes; HD 92/43: 62A0 Eastern sub-Mediterranean dry grasslands (*Scorzoneretalia villosae*)). The main reason for exploring this type of habitat was that certain species which are present across the border with Bulgaria at Chepan Mt, for example *Charissa mutilata* (Staudinger, 1878), *Hadena vulcanica urumovi* (Drenowski, 1931), *Rhyacia arenacea* (Hampson, 1907) etc., had not been found in Serbia. We assumed, or were almost sure, that they would occur in the same habitat over the border in Serbia and the only reason that they had not been found there was a failure to search in appropriate localities at a suitable time. Some of these species had recently already been found (Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2022) and some are published here now. We looked several times in September for *Eumera regina* Staudinger, 1892 and *Eugnorisma pontica* (Staudinger, 1892) in Serbia – species present in Bulgaria near the border to Serbia. *Eugnorisma pontica* was found and is published here and, in addition, we found another new species for Serbia – *Perizoma flavosparsata uniformata* Mentzer, 1974, which is not present in Bulgaria and in coming years we will search for it near the Serbian border in Bulgaria. In North Macedonia, we looked six times in November–

December for *Erannis declinans* (Staudinger, 1879), a species well presented in Bulgaria but not found yet across the border in North Macedonia. Another species, presented in SW Bulgaria, but not found yet in North Macedonia and Albania is *Chemerina calliginearia* (Rambur, 1833), for which we looked twice in these countries in March, but without success. The situation with *Eochoroca balcanica* (Rebel in Prinz, 1919) and *Bryophila seladona burgeffi* (Draudt, 1931) is similar – they are present in North Macedonia close to the border with Albania, but not found in Albania yet, although we looked for them several times in September.

Materials and methods

The night-time collecting methods since 2011 have involved 2 portable light traps with an 8 watt “Blacklight” white tube (368 nm) and 8 watt “Blacklight” black tube, both powered by 12 volt 9Ah batteries, as well as a Finnish “tent trap” with a 160 watt MV bulb at the top of the pole and a 20 watt (368 nm) black light lamp over the catching pot below, powered by a generator (Fig. 1). An additional 20-watt (368 nm) (from 2022 EntoLight UV-LED E27-300 mm 8 Watt 365–375 nm and 395–405 nm) lamp was also positioned about 70-90m from the tent trap. The distance between the Finnish “tent trap” and the light traps, as well as between the light traps themselves, was sometimes several hundred meters, as they were deployed with different outlooks wherever possible. All traps ran throughout the night. From the second half of August 2022 onwards the Finnish “tent trap” was furnished with LepiLED, a 1.5 maxi model UV LED lamp with adapter and transformer 220 – 12V, powered by a generator.

Morphological methods. Genitalia were extracted and mounted on glass slides in Euparal after staining with a 2% Merbromin solution. All genitalia slides were photographed with a Zeiss stereo microscope Stemi 2000-C with Canon 2000 digital camera and transmitted light; the single illustrated everted vesicae and, in the most cases, the female genitalia were photographed in alcohol before mounting on glass in Euparal. Specimens and collecting localities were photographed with a Sony DSChX400v digital camera; for specimens the scale line is 1 cm. Unless indicated otherwise, material was collected by S. Beshkov and A. Nahirnić-Beshkova (before October, 2020 as A.

Nahirnić) and, together with the genitalia slides, are part of the collections of the authors in the NMNHS (National Museum of Natural History, Sofia).

Lepidoptera families are arranged according to Aarvik et al. (2017, 2021). The sequence and nomenclature of families Erebidae and Noctuidae follow Fibiger et al. (2011), with changes incorporated from subsequent taxonomic revisions and the recently published books of Top et al. (2023) and Ronkay et al. (2024). The Geometridae are arranged according to Hausmann & Sihvonen (2019). When a specimen's number is indicated, it refers to the collection of Stoyan Beshkov in the NMNHS. In the systematic part below, countries are arranged from West to East, and localities in the countries are also placed in this way. If are only one or two species reported from a particular locality, the locality is presented with its full data for the species and is not included in the list of the localities. Collecting localities are illustrated if they have not been illustrated before in our articles for Albania, North Macedonia and Serbia, or were not explored before at all, but are inhabited by interesting species and need further investigation. All trips abroad were self-financed by the authors and undertaken in their own time. In Bulgaria, part of the trips were financed from the Project "Biodiversity of target insect groups (Coleoptera, Hymenoptera and Lepidoptera) and their pathogens from different habitats in Bulgaria" (grant KP-06-N51/1-18.08.2022) and some other projects.

List of localities

Bosnia and Herzegovina

Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Republika Srpska, Trebinje Municipality, Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 659 m, N42.7272, E018.385, *Quercus*, *Acer monspessulanum*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Fraxinus ornus* on limestone area (Fig. 1).

Tovarnica Mt, near Mrgudići – Brda – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Republika Srpska, Tovarnica Mt, near Mrgudići – Brda, 751 m, N43.6947, E019.1153, *Quercus* forest.

Višegrad, Jegrlići – Bosnia and Herzegovina, Republika Srpska, Višegrad Municipality, Jegrlići, 572 m, N43.78173, E019.27096, *Quercus-Carpinus* forest and meadows with orchards.

Montenegro (Crna Gora)

Ostroška Greda, near Povija – Montenegro, Nikšić Municipality, Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 593 m, N42.6866, E019.0007, *Quercus*, *Acer monspessulanum*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Fraxinus ornus* on limestone area (Fig. 2).

Durmitor Mts, Veliki Štuoc – Montenegro, Durmitor Mts, below Veliki Štuoc summit, 1993 m, N43.1881, E019.0586, limestone subalpine area.

Pirlitor, near Vrela – Montenegro, Žabljak Region, Uskočki Canyon, Pirlitor, near Vrela Village, 1248 m, N43.1641, E019.2239, limestone rocks and a dry meadow near coniferous forest.

Drume, Tuzi Municipality – Montenegro, Skadarsko jezero lake surroundings, Tuzi Municipality near Drume Village, 193 m, N42.3375, E019.3676, *Punica*, *Phyllirea*, *Quercus*, *Paliurus*, *Fraxinus ornus* on limestone area (Fig. 3).

Ski Centre above Kolašin – Montenegro, Bjelasica Mts, Kolašin Region, above Ski Centre, 1931 m, N42.8543, E019.6566, subalpine meadows with *Vaccinium* and rocky slopes (Fig. 4).

Rožaje, Vrelo Ibra – Montenegro, Rožaje, Vrelo Ibra, 1248 m, N42.7976, E020.0905, *Abies alba*, *Fagus*, *Acer*, *Petasites* in deep river valley (Fig. 5).

Albania

Shkodra Lake, Kosan – Albania, Shkodra Lake, Kodra e Vaut near Kosan Village, 8 m, N43.2643, E019.3767, lake shore with *Juncus*, *Mentha*, and low vegetation (Fig. 6).

Cape of Rodon – Albania, Adriatic Sea Coast, near Shetaj Village, Cape of Rodon (= Kepi i Rodonit), 109 m, N41.5525, E019.4728, Maquis with *Erica arborea*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Quercus ilex*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Cystus*.

Fier, above Radostinë Village – Albania, Fier Region, above Radostinë Village, 78 m, N40.7252, E019.5069, *Olea*, *Paliurus*, *Quercus*, *Spartium junceum* on sandy ground (Fig. 7).

Llogara, 1240m – Albania, Vlora Region, Llogara, below the antennae, 1240 m, N40.199, E019.5799, limestone slopes above the sea with *Buxus*, *Juniperus*, *Pinus*, low vegetation (Fig. 8).

Lushnja, above Ardenica – Albania, Lushnja County, above Ardenica Village, 127 m, N40.8265, E019.5882, open areas with vineyards, *Olea*, *Paliurus*, in high maquis.

Fig. 1. Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village.

Fig. 2. Ostroška Greda, near Povija.

Fig. 3. Drume, Tuzi Municipality.

Fig. 4. Ski Centre above Kolašin.

Fig. 5. Rožaje, Vrelo Ibra.

Fig. 6. Shkodra Lake, Kosan.

Fig. 7. Fier, above Radostinë Village.

Fig. 8. Llogara, 1240 m, May.

Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm – Albania, Vlora Region, Lungar Mt, Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm Village, 362 m, N40.3050, E019.6384, *Quercus coccifera*, *Paliurus*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Colutaea*, *Spartium*, *Arbutus* (Fig. 9).

Himara, above Kudhes – Albania, Himara Municipality, above Kudhes Village, 376 m, N40.0804, E019.7921, limestone slopes with *Phlomis fruticosa*, *Quercus coccifera*, *Q. macrolepis*, low vegetation (Fig. 10).

Tepelene, above Nivice Village – Albania, Tepelene Region, above Nivice Village, 1150 m, N40.2679, E019.8864, slopes with *Phlomis fruticosa* and low vegetation (Fig. 11).

Maja e Manjolave – Albania, Skenderbeg Mt, Qafe Shtamë Pass, Maja e Manjolave below, 1131 m, N41.5052, E019.9099, limestone slopes with *Quercus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Acer*, *Juniperus oxycedrus* (Fig. 12).

Progonat – Albania, Tepelene Region, near Progonat Village, 992 m, N40.2222, E019.9245, rocky limestone slopes with *Quercus coccifera* (Fig. 13).

Puke, Terbunit Mts – Albania, Shkodra Region, Terbunit Mts, Sucelit Ridge near Puke, 1096 m, N42.0279, E019.9332, 25.VIII.2023, serpentinite with *Quercus*, *Pinus nigra*, *Pteridium*, open areas (Fig. 14).

Qafa e Pashkasheshit above Iba – Albania, Tirana Region, Qafa e Pashkasheshit above Iba Village, 727 m, N41.2439, E019.9779, limestone area with *Carpinus orientalis*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Acer monspessulanum*, *Juniperus*, etc. (Fig. 15).

Ksamil – Albania, Ionian Sea Coast, N of Ksamil Town, 67 m, N39.7965, E020.0032, maquis with *Olea*, *Phlomis fruticosa*, etc. (Fig. 16).

Butrint – Albania, Ionian Sea Coast, Butrint, 42 m, N39.7464, E020.0151, limestone slopes with *Phlomis fruticosa*, *Paliurus*, *Olea*, low vegetation (Fig. 17).

Tepelene Region, Drino River – Albania, Tepelene Region, Drino River near the confluence to Vjosa, 137 m, N40.2629, E020.0539, river valley with *Platanus*, *Salix*, etc.

Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village – Albania, Tomori Mts, below Tomori i Madh Village above Poliçan, 686 m, N40.6955, E020.0814, 15.VI.2024, dry slopes with *Cystus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Erica arborea*, *Cotinus coggigria*, *Pistacia*, *Juniperus oxycedrus* (Fig. 18).

Mali me Gropa, 1466 m – Albania, Tirana Region, Mali me Gropa Mt, 1466 m, N41.3508, E020.0901, meadows with dolines near *Fagus* forest on limestone area (Fig. 19).

Këlcyrës Gorge on Aaos River – Albania, Gjirokastër Region, Gryka e Këlcyrës (Klisura) Gorge on Aaos (Vjosa) River near Këlçirë (Klisura) Village, 176 m, N40.29646, E020.16260, river valley with *Platanus orientalis*, *Alnus glutinosa* and maquis.

Gjirokaster, between Mal Çajup and Erind – Albania, Gjirokaster County, Mt Lunxhërisë between Mal Çajup and Erind Village, 1028 m, N40.1815, E020.1673, mountain steppe with *Quercus*, *Carpinus*, *Acer* trees around.

Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top – Albania, Tomori Mts, above Ujanik Village and below Abaz Ali Top, 1894 m, N40.6171, E020.1851, mountain meadows and rocky slopes on limestone areas (Fig. 20).

Tomori Mts, above Korita Village – Albania, Tomori Mts, above Çorovoda, above Korita Village, 1242 m, N40.5522, E020.2695, limestone slopes with *Carpinus orientalis*, *Corylus*, *Acer*, *Morina persica*, *Juniperus oxycedrus* (Fig. 21).

Devoli Gorge, near Bratilë – Albania, Devoli Gorge, near Bratilë Village, Gramsh Region, 519 m, N40.7708, E020.3104, *Phyllirea*, *Cotinus*, *Erica*, *Pistacia*, *Buxus*, *Carpinus*, *Quercus ilex*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Paliurus*, *Cystus*, etc.

Kukës County, W of Ploshtan – Albania, Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, Maja Kufla e Sina, 1257 m, N41.8438, E020.4127, meadows and *Corylus avellana* (Fig. 22).

Benjë-Novoselë near Petran – Albania, Permet County, Benjë-Novoselë near Petran, 437 m, N40.2442, E020.4228, Maquis, *Arbutus unedo*, *Pistacia*.

Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq – Albania, Korçë County, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq Village, 1236 m, N40.5322, E020.5979, stony slopes with *Acer monspessulanum*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus trojana*, etc. (Fig. 23).

Prrenjas-Pogradec, near Qafa Kotodeshit – Albania, Prrenjas-Pogradec, near Qafa Kotodeshit, 1132 m, N41.0426, E020.6030, dry meadows with *Juniperus* near young *Quercus* forest (Fig. 24).

Maja Ahishtes Geges – Albania, Pogradec Region, above Ohrid Lake, below Maja Ahishtes Geges,

Fig. 9. Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm.

Fig. 10. Himara, above Kudhes.

Fig. 11. Tepelene, above Nivice Village.

Fig. 12. Maja e Manjolave.

Fig. 13. Progonat.

Fig. 14. Puke, Terbunit Mts.

Fig. 15. Qafa e Pashkasheshit above Iba.

Fig. 16. Ksamil.

Fig. 17. Butrint.

Fig. 18. Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village.

Fig. 19. Mali me Gropa, 1466 m.

Fig. 20. Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top.

Fig. 21. Tomori Mts, above Korita Village.

Fig. 22. Kukës County, W of Ploshtan.

Fig. 23. Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq.

Fig. 24. Prrenjas-Pogradec, near Qafa Kotodeshit.

1323 m, N40.998, E020.6087, open stony area with *Quercus dalechampii*, *J. oxycedrus*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Pinus*, etc.

Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes – Albania, Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 1316 m, N40.8437, E020.6216, open area in mixed *Fagus* forest.

Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes – Albania, Pogradec county, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 1185 m, N40.8561, E020.631, slopes with *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, meadows with *Pteridium* (Fig. 25).

Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula – Albania, Pogradec Region, Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 781 m, N41.0587, E020.6481, limestone area with *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus trojana*, *Quercus sp.*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Castanea sativa*, etc. (Fig. 26).

Mt. Kuq, below Qarrit Pass – Albania, Korçë – Colonje, Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass near Qarrit Village, 903 m, N40.4597; E020.6528, stony slopes in river valley with *Juniperus*, *Artemisia alba*, *Pinus nigra*, *Quercus pubescens*, etc. (Fig. 27).

Ersekë County, above Borovë – Albania, Ersekë County, above Borovë Village, 1096 m, N40.2977, E020.6594, stream, meadows and stony slopes with *Astracantha* near coniferous forest.

Galičica Mts, above Bregas – Albania Mali i Thatë (= Galičica Mts) above Bregas (= Korita) Village, 1374 m, N40.8055, E020.8342, dry rocky grassland on slopes with scarce vegetation (Fig. 28).

Prespa Lake, near Glloboçeni Village – Albania, Prespa Lake, near Glloboçeni (= Gollomboç) Village, 930-951 m, N40.8456, E020.9239, meadow in *Quercus trojana*, *Acer monspessulanum*, *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. oxycedrus*, *Dictamnus alba*, etc., forest (Fig. 29).

Prespa e vogel near Tren – Albania, Liqeni Prespa e vogel near Tren Village, 858 m, N40.67466, E020.989, swamp with *Phragmites* and single poplar trees and limestone slopes around with *Buxus*, *Carpinus*, *Ephedra*, *Salvia*, etc. This place is the Visitors Centre of the Liqeni Prespa e vogel Natural Park and we used to collect there only in rain under the eaves of the building, which is not in use (Fig. 30).

Greece

Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi – Greece, Macedonia Province, above Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 1808 m, N40.7912, E021.2755, mountain slopes with meadows above *Fagus* forest (Fig. 31).

Serbia

Monastery Rača above Bajina Bašta – Serbia, Monastir Rača above Bajina Bašta, 526 m, N43.9299, E019.5325, *Fagus-Acer*-coniferous forest, meadow, stream.

Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula – Serbia, Prijepolje Municipality, Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula Village, 1374 m, N43.3191, E019.8309, 30.VI.2024, limestone area, rocks, meadow with *Juniperus communis* and *Picea abies* forest around.

Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača – Serbia, Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 1762 m, N43.2978, E020.3927, meadows and *Pteridium* in coniferous forest (Fig. 32).

above Veliki Čukar, 982 m – Serbia, Kraljevo Region, above Kamenica Village, Stolovi Mt, above Veliki Čukar, 982 m, N43.5968, E020.6579, *Fagus*, *Quercus*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Centaurea calocephala*, meadows.

Veliki Čukar – Serbia, Kraljevo Region, above Kamenica Village, Stolovi Mt, Veliki Čukar, 688 m, N43.6019, E020.6855, Serpenenite with *Silene*, *Artemisia*, *Quercus*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Acer tataricum*, *Centaurea calocephala*.

Straža – Serbia, Kučajske Planine, Garje near Straža, 744 m, N43.884, E021.7034, meadows with *Crataegus* near *Fagus* forest.

Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 825 m – Serbia, Sokobanja, Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac Village, 885 m, N43.75875, E021.88979, limestone slopes with *Prunus spinosa*, *Syringa vulgaris*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Quercus*, *Artemisia alba*, etc.

Pčinja River Valley, Vražji Kamen near Trgovište – Serbia, Dolina Reka Pčinje, Vražji Kamen near Trgovište Village, 663 m, N42.385, E022.0517, silicate rocks near *Quercus* forest.

Suva Planina, Divna Gorica – Serbia, Suva Planina, Preslap, Divna Gorica above Bela Palanka Town, 1186 m, N43.19473, E022.244, dry limestone rocky slopes with *Artemisia alba* above *Fagus* forest, two light traps (Fig. 33).

Suva Planina above Bela Palanka – Serbia, Suva Planina above Bela Palanka, 504 m, N43.1975, E022.2835, meadows in *Acer monspessulanum*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus* forest on limestone ground.

Bela Palanka, above Moklište – Serbia, Svrliške Planine Mts, Bela Palanka Municipality, above Moklište Village, 684 m, N43.2817, E022.294, limestone slopes with *Artemisia alba* and *Carpinus* forest.

Fig. 25. Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes.

Fig. 26. Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula.

Fig. 27. Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass in May.

Fig. 28. Galičica Mts, above Bregas.

Fig. 29. Prespa Lake, near Glloboçeni Village, November.

Fig. 30. Prespa e vogel near Tren in June.

Fig. 31. Vigla.

Fig. 32. Golija Mts.

Fig. 33. Suva Planina, Divna Gorica.

Fig. 34. Šljivovički Vis.

Šljivovički Vis – Serbia, Bela Palanka Municipality, Šljivovički Vis, above Šljivovik Village, 925 m, N43.1414, E022.3867, limestone area with meadows with *Artemisia alba*, *Crataegus*, etc. (Fig. 34).

Vidlič, below Crni Vrh – Serbia, Pirot Region, Vidlič Mts, below Crni Vrh Summit, 1046 m, N43.1808, E022.6478, limestone area with *Acer monspessulanum*, *Quercus*, *Syringa*, *Artemisia alba*, *Crataegus*, etc.

Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod) – Serbia, Vištin Kamen between Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod) and Bačevo, 763 m, N43.0271, E022.8239, limestone slopes and disused quarry with *Artemisia alba* near *Quercus-Carpinus* forest (Fig. 35).

Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci – Serbia, Vidlič Mt, Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), Jankov Dol above Smilovci Village, 953 m, N43.09903, E022.86374, stony slopes with *Fraxinus ornus* near *Quercus-Carpinus* forest (Fig. 36).

North Macedonia

Prilep, Pletvar Pass – North Macedonia, Prilep Region, Babuna Planina, Pletvar Pass, 965 m, N41.3701, E021.6698, marble rocky area with *Artemisia*, *Quercus trojana*, *Ulmus*, etc.

Dračev Dol, below Rebre – North Macedonia, Tikveš, Gradsko district, Dračev Dol, below Rebre Village, 204 m, N41.6462, E021.8366, hills with *Paliurus*, *Astracantha*, *Pyrus*, *Pistacia*, *Platanus*, etc. (Fig. 37).

Bulgaria

Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets – Bulgaria, Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets Top on the road from Ossogovo Hotel to Ruen Top, 1630 m, N42.1888, E022.617, small stream in subalpine slopes with *Verbascum*, *Chamaecytisus*, *Pinus*, *Salix*, *Rubus idaeus*, ruderal.

W Stara Planina, Gorni Lom – Martinovo – Bulgaria, W Stara Planina Mts, above Gorni Lom Village on the road to Martinovo, 743 m, N43.4325, E022.7419, forest and meadows in a river valley.

Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro – Bulgaria, Kraishte, between Breznik and Trun towns, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro Village, 1049 m, N42.73487, E022.77677, limestone slopes with *Artemisia alba*, *Syringa*, etc.

Chepan, Petrovski Krust – Bulgaria, Dragoman Municipality, Chepan Mt, below Petrovski Krust

Summit, 1167 m, N42.94797, E022.95211, limestone slopes with *Silene*, *Satureja*, *Syringa*, *Artemisia alba*, *Amygdalus nana*, *Centaurea*, *Crataegus*, *Stipa*, *Rosa* [Mountain petrophytic steppes 02E1].

Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir – Bulgaria, Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir Town, below Orлите Chalet, 878 m, N42.5683, E022.9726, stony slopes with *Artemisia alba*, *Syringa*, *Crataegus*, *Quercus*, *Pyrus*, etc. (Fig. 38).

Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila – Bulgaria, Golo Burdo Mt, Golata Mogila above Radomir Town, 1012 m, N42.55913, E023.007, stony slopes with *Artemisia alba*, *Syringa*, *Crataegus*, *Pyrus*, etc. (Fig. 39).

Slivnitsa, above Aldomirovsko Blato – Bulgaria, Slivnitsa Municipality, above Aldomirovsko Blato swamp, 733 m, N42.9018, E023.0191, limestone slopes with *Silene*, *Satureja*, *Syringa*, *Artemisia alba*, *Amygdalus nana*, *Centaurea*, *Crataegus*, *Stipa*, *Rosa*, etc.

Lyulin Mts, above Dragichevo – Bulgaria, Lyulin Mts, Pernik Region, above Dragichevo Village, 905 m, N42.6205, E023.1611, meadow in *Quercus* forest.

above Bosnek – Bulgaria, Vitosha Mt, Golyamata Mogila above Bosnek Village, 1197 m, N42.5032, E023.1936, 24.VIII.2024, meadows and stony slopes with *Satureja* and *Artemisia alba*, etc. near *Fagus* forest (Fig. 40).

Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlazi – Bulgaria, Struma River Valley – S Pirin Mts, above Kresna Town from the road to Vlazi Village, 553 m, N41.7321, E023.1998, slopes with *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. oxycedrus*, *Quercus*, etc.

Rila, above Karagyol reservoir below Kalin Peak – Bulgaria, Rila Mts, above Pastra Village, above Karagyol reservoir, below Kalin Peak, 2552 m, N42.1824, E023.2566, alpine-subalpine meadows and rocky slopes (Fig. 41).

Marino Pole – SW Bulgaria, Struma Valley, above Marino Pole Village, 197 m, N41.4203, E023.3515, sandy soil with *Quercus*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Prunus*, *Paliurus*, vineyards (Fig. 42).

Rila, near Makedonia Chalet – Bulgaria, Rila Mts, Blagoevgrad Region, the pass near Makedonia Chalet, 2197 m, N42.0527, E023.4109, subalpine slopes with *Pinus mugo*, *Chamaecytisus absinthioides*, *Verbascum*.

S. Pirin, Hrasna – SW Bulgaria, S Pirin Mts, above Gorno Spanchevo Village, near Hrasna Village,

Fig. 35. Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad, August.

Fig. 36. Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, September.

Fig. 37. Dračev Dol, below Rebre, June.

Fig. 38. Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, May.

Fig. 39. Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila.

Fig. 40. above Bosnek.

Fig. 41. Rila, above Karagyol reservoir.

Fig. 42. Marino Pole.

610 m, N41.4905, E023.5095, *Quercus*, *Juniperus*, *Cystus*, meadows.

S Pirin – Alibotoush Mts, above Petrovo – Bulgaria, S Pirin – Alibotoush Mts, above Petrovo Village, 855 m, N41.4067, E023.5724, meadows in limestone area with *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus* etc.

Alibotush, above Goleshovo – Bulgaria, Slavyanka Mts (= Alibotush Mts), beginning of the ground road to Livada, above Goleshovo Village, 1020 m, N41.4058, E023.5889, meadows with *Juniperus* and *Quercus*.

Alibotush, below Livada – Bulgaria, Slavyanka Mts (= Alibotush), below Livada, 1600 m, N41.4079, E023.6105, open area with *Salix* in coniferous forest on limestone area.

Novo Leski – Bulgaria, Mesta Valley, SE Pirin, Sveti Iliya above Novo Leski Village, Gotse Delchev district, 698 m, N41.5264, E023.7738, slopes with *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Quercus*, meadows.

Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village – Bulgaria, Stargach Mts, above Ilinden Village, 716 m, N41.4599, E023.7902, *Quercus*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Artemisia alba*, stony meadows (Fig. 43).

W. Rhodopi Mts, above Trigrad Gorge – Bulgaria, Western Rhodopi Mts, Trigrad Gorge, above Dyavolskoto Gurlo cave, 1278 m, N41.6119, E024.3781, limestone rocky slopes with *Juniperus* and *Morina persica* near coniferous forest.

Krichim, Izgoryaloto Gyune – Bulgaria, Rhodopi Mts, Izgoryaloto Gyune Reserve above Krichim Town, 407 m, N42.0239, E024.4683, slopes with *Pistacia*, *Quercus*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Paliurus*, *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Colutea*, etc. (Fig. 44).

E Rhodopi, Zhenda, The rock mushroom – Bulgaria, E Rhodopi Mts, Komuniga Municipality, Zhenda Village, The rock mushroom near Sokolite Suburb, 770 m, N41.7642, E025.1755, rocky place with *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, pastures (Fig. 45).

E. Rhodopi, Egrek – Bulgaria, Eastern Rhodopi Mts, “Livada” above Egrek Village, 573 m, N41.3181, E025.6336, stony slopes with *Juniperus oxycedrus* and *Quercus-Carpinus* forest on limestone area.

Meandrite na Byala Reka – Bulgaria, Eastern Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad district, Meandrite na Byala Reka River near Meden Buk Village, 121 m,

N41.3827, E026.0225, *Alnus glutinosa*, *Salix*, *Quercus*, *Cystus*, etc.

Sheynovets above Mezek – Bulgaria, Eastern Rhodopi Mts, Svilengrad district, Sheynovets above Mezek Village, 539 m, N41.7178, E026.0627, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Phyllirea*, *Syringa*, *Genista*, *Peonia*, *Jasminum*, *Quercus*, *Asparagus acutifolius*, etc.

E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana – Bulgaria, E Rhodopi Mts, Likana (Kodzhakaya) between Odrintsi and Byalo Pole villages, Ivaylovgrad district, 274 m, N41.4456, E026.1369, limestone area with *Phyllirea*, *Juniperus*, *Acer monspessulanum*, *Quercus*, meadows (Fig. 46).

Sakar Mt, below Vishegrad, near Kostur – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, below Vishegrad Summit, near Kostur Village, 715 m, N41.9966, E026.2657, meadows in *Quercus* forest.

Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad Town, 344 m, N42.0975, E026.3252, limestone slopes with *Paliurus*, *Carpinus*, *Quercus*, scarce low grass vegetation.

Sakar, Shtit – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, near Shtit Village, 248 m, N41.8396, E026.3393, sandy slopes with *Pistacia*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Quercus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Paliurus*, *Pyrus amigdalifolia*, *Astragalus*, etc. (Fig. 47).

Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, “Mogilata” near Shtit Village, 290 m, N41.8439, E026.3457, grassy slopes with *Pistacia*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Quercus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Paliurus*, *Pyrus amigdalifolia*, *Astragalus*, *Dictamnus albus*, etc.

Sakar, NW of Shtit – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, NW of Shtit Village, 291 m, N41.8296, E026.3496, *Quercus*, *Paliurus*, meadows.

Sakar, Oreshnik – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, above Oreshnik Village, below Damkaya, 396 m, N42.0517, E026.3615, meadows with *Pistacia*, *Quercus*, *Paliurus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, etc.

Sakar, near Mramor Village – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, disused quarry near Mramor Village, 203 m, N42.0348, E026.4116, slopes with marble rocks and *Pistacia*, *Quercus*, *Paliurus*, *Pyrus amigdalifolia*, *Carpinus orientalis*, etc. (Fig. 48).

Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, SE below Mihalich Village, near the antennifer, 316 m, N41.8533, E026.4381, *Paliurus*, *Jasminum*, *Pistacia*, *Pyrus*, *Amigdalus*, *Ulmus*, grassland (Fig. 49).

Sakar, above Sladun Village – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, above Sladun Village, 174 m, N41.8485, E026.4858,

Fig. 43. Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village.

Fig. 44. Krichim, Izgoryaloto Gyune.

Fig. 45. E Rhodopi, Zhenda, The rock mushroom.

Fig. 46. E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana.

Fig. 47. Sakar, Shtit, May.

Fig. 48. Sakar, near Mramor Village, May.

Fig. 49. Sakar, SE below Mihalich.

Fig. 50. Sakar, above Karabashka Reka, June.

Fig. 51. E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo.

Fig. 52. N Black Sea Coast, Cape Kaliakra, disused well.

slopes with *Pistacia*, *Quercus*, *Paliurus*, *Pyrus amigdalifolia*, *Cotinus coggygria*, *Salvia nutans*, *Euphorbia*, etc.

NW above Glushnik Village – Bulgaria, Sliven Region, Grebenets Natura 2000 Protected area, NW above Glushnik Village, above the graveyard, 243 m, N42.6647, E026.4944, slopes with *Paliurus*, *Pistacia*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Astracantha*, *Pinus*, *Ulmus*, etc.

Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik – Bulgaria, Sakar Mt, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik villages, 188 m, N41.8525, E026.4991, sandy slopes with *Pistacia*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Quercus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Paliurus*, *Pyrus amigdalifolia*, etc. (Fig. 50).

E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo, 566m – Bulgaria, E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo Village, 566 m, N42.6848, E026.5698, meadows with *Paliurus*, *Quercus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Syringa vulgaris*, *Astragalus angustifolius* (Fig. 51).

E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo, 491m – Bulgaria, E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo Village, 491 m, N42.6864, E026.5735, meadows with *Paliurus*, *Quercus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Syringa vulgaris*, *Astragalus angustifolius*, daytime collecting only.

Atanassovsko Ezero Lake – Bulgaria, S Black Sea Coast, Burgass Region, Atanassovsko Ezero Lake, Solnitsite near Rudnik Chernomore, 10 m, N42.5782, E027.4949, *Phragmites*, *Atrémisia*, *Salicornia*, etc.

Suhata Reka above Kapitan Dimitrovo – Bulgaria, Dobrogea, Suhata Reka, above Kapitan Dimitrovo Village, 148 m, N43.9533, E027.7036, steppe and steppe-like area with ruderal.

Strandzha, Popovi Skali – Bulgaria, Strandzha Mts, Trionska Reka between Fazanovo and Velika villages, near Popovi Skali, 56 m, N42.1638, E027.7361, stony slopes near river with *Paliurus*, *Phyllirea*, etc.

Strandzha, “Pirena” above Kosti – Bulgaria, Strandzha Mts, “Dedo Vulcho, Pirena” above Kosti Village, 283 m, N42.0924, E027.79, warm hill with *Cystus*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Quercus*, etc.

Strandzha Mts, Papiya – Bulgaria, Strandzha Mts – S. Black Sea Coast, Papiya above Brodilovo Village, 439 m, N42.1053, E027.8453, *Quercus* forest with *Phyllirea*, *Cystus*, etc.

Silvercoast, “Bukvite” above Balchik – Bulgaria, N Black Sea Coast, Silvercoast, Bukvite above

Balchik Town, 177 m, N43.40689, E028.17666, sandy rocks with *Atrémisia*, etc. S. Beshkov, R. Wasala & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova leg.

N Black Sea Coast, between Cape Kaliakra and Bulgarevo – Bulgaria, N Black Sea Coast, between Cape Kaliakra and Bulgarevo Village, 87 m, N43.3937, E028.4311, steppe area with bushes and ruderal vegetation.

N Black Sea Coast, Cape Kaliakra, disused well – Bulgaria, N Black Sea Coast, Cape Kaliakra, disused well, 73 m, N43.3822, E028.4465, vertical sediment slopes in steppe area with bushes and ruderal vegetation (Fig. 52).

Systematics

Hepialidae

Triodia amasinus dobrogensis (Caradja, 1932) Bulgaria: Meandrite na Byala Reka, 06.X.2022, 3 males. It is known from this area in September (Beshkov & Goater, 2000). This is the latest flight period known for this taxon.

Psychidae

Melasina melana (Frivaldszky, 1837) Bulgaria: Ossogovo Mts, below Ruen Top, 2039 m, N42.17292, E022.55659, 21.VII.2024, subalpine meadows, at daytime, 1 female (Fig. 53).

Bijugis bombicella ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024, 3 males.

Fig. 53. *Melasina melana* ♀. BG, Ruen 21.VII.2024.

Fig. 54. *Scardia boletella* ♀. BG, Ossogovo Kunets 21.VII.2024.

Tineidae

Scardia boletella (Fabricius, 1794) Bulgaria: Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets, 21.VII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 54).

Brachodidae

Brachodes tristis (Staudinger, 1879) Bulgaria: Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male; S. Pirin, Hrasna, 30.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 55). In Bulgaria *Brachodes tristis* had been reported only from Kresna Gorge (Sheytan Dere) and Lilyanovo Village above Sandanski Town (Kallies & Spatenka, 2002). Second report for Bulgaria.

Brachodes pumilus (Esper, 1783) Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 27.VII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 56).

Sesiidae

Negotinthia myrmosaeformis myrmosaeformis (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male.

Cossidae

Stygoides colchica (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) Bulgaria: E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo, 491 m, 03.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 57) at daytime. This species was previously known in Bulgaria from a single specimen only from Eastern Rhodopi, Madzharovo

Fig. 55. *Brachodes tristis* ♂. BG, Hrasna 30.VI.2023.

Fig. 56. *Brachodes pumila* ♀. BG, Chepan 27.VII.2024.

Fig. 57. *Stygoides colchica* ♂. BG, Sedlarevo 03.VI.2023.

Fig. 58. *Phragmataecia castanea* ♂. AL, Kosan 02.VII.2024.

Fig. 59. *Phragmataecia castaneae* ♀. AL, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

(Beshkov & Langourov, 2004). Second locality for Bulgaria. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is critically endangered in Bulgaria – CR B2ab(iii).

Phragmataecia castaneae (Hübner, 1790) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 58); Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 males and 1 female (Fig. 59). Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 male; Atanassovsko Ezero Lake, 30.VII.2022, 2 males.

Thyrididae

Thyris fenestrella (Scopoli, 1763) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Hesperiidae

Pyrgus serratulae (Rambur, [1839]) Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 female.

Pyrgus cinarae (Rambur, [1839]) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male.

Pieridae

Euchloe ausonia (Hübner, [1804]) Bulgaria: Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 02.V.2024.

Lycaenidae

Cacyreus marshalli Butler, [1898] Albania: Korçë, Centre of the Town, N40°36'56", E20°46'30", 870 m, 26–27.IX.2024.

Plebejus sephirus (Frivaldszky, 1835) Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 2 males and 2 females; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 24.V.2024, 2 males. New species for Golo Bardo; Sakar, Shtit, 17.V.2024, 3 males. New species for Sakar Mt, not present in the articles of Kiriakov (1988) and Abadjiev (2001).

Plebejus eumedon (Esper, [1780]) Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, Ponichka near Hlyabovo Village, 410 m, N42.0529, E026.2681, 20.V.2024, meadow with *Geranium sanguineum*, abundant. This is also the lowest locality of this species in Bulgaria. New species for Sakar Mt, not present in the articles of Kiriakov (1988) and Abadjiev (2001).

Plebejus anteros (Freyer, 1838) Bulgaria: Kostinbrod Municipality, near Ponor Village, 917 m, N42.91524, E023.1287, 20.X.2024, stony slopes with *Artemisia alba* on limestone area, 1 male.

Polyommatus semiargus (Rottemburg, 1775) Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024. New species for Sakar Mt, not present in the articles of Kiriakov (1988) or Abadjiev (2001).

Nymphalidae

Erebia melas (Herbst, 1796) Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024.

Melanargia larissa (Geyer, [1828]) Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024.

Melanargia russiae (Esper, 1783) Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 1 female.

Nymphalis vaualbum ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Vištin Kamen between Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod) Town and Bačevo Village, 764 m, N43.0281, E022.8240, 30.III.2024, limestone slopes with *Artemisia alba* and *Crataegus* in mixed *Quercus-Carpinus* forest, a single specimen observed during the daytime. *Nymphalis vaualbum* is a priority species, included in Annexes II and IV of the EC Habitat Directive 92/43.

Brenthis ino (Rottemburg, 1775) Bulgaria: Lyulin Mt, between Cherniya Kos and Lyulin villa areas, N42°39'09", E23°12'17", 951 m, 29.VI.2023, A. Nahirić-Beshkova leg., *Festuco-Agrostetum* Horvat 1951, Natura 2000 habitat type 6520 Mountain hay meadows.

Brenthis hecate ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, Ponichka near Hlyabovo Village, 410 m, N42.0529, E026.2681, 20.V.2024, meadows. New species for Sakar Mt, not present in the articles of Kiriakov (1988) and Abadjiev (2001).

Melitaea arduinna rhodopensis Freyer, [1836] Bulgaria: Sakar, above Sladun Village, 18.V.2024, 1 male. New species for Sakar Mt, not present in the articles of Kiriakov (1988) and Abadjiev (2021). According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is vulnerable in Bulgaria – VU B2ab(iii).

Melitaea ornata Christoph, 1893 Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 female, aberrant; Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.V.2024. A new species for Sakar Mt, not present in Kiriakov (1988) and Abadjiev (2001).

Melitaea athalia (Rottemburg, 1775) Bulgaria: Sofia Region, Kostinbrod Municipality, above Beledie Han, near the crossroad to Ponor Village, 906 m, N42.9127, E023.165, meadow with *S. vulgaris*, *Crataegus monogyna*, etc, 22.VI.2024, 1 male aberrant (Fig. 60), genitalia checked.

Euphydryas aurinia (Rottemburg, 1775) Greece: Macedonia, Vigla, between Florina and Pisoderi, 1787 m, N40.7939, E021.2725, 10.VII.2018, mountain meadows; Ibid, 1695 m, N40.7867, E021.2733, 10.VII.2018, mountain meadows; Thrace Province, Eastern Rhodopi Mts, near Avdella Village between Kiprinos and Metaxades, 167 m, N41°25'47", E026°12'03", 01.V.2014, open areas with *Quercus*, *Phyllirea*, *Pistacia*, *Colutea*, S. Beshkov & S. Abadjiev leg.; Ibid, disused quarry near Metaxades Vil-

Fig. 60. *Melitaea athalia* ♂. BG, Ponor 22.VI.2024.

Fig. 61. *Euphydryas aurinia* ♂. GR, Avdela 30.IV.2019.

Fig. 62. *Loryma egregialis* ♂. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023.

lage, 113 m, N41.4245, E026.2129, 30.IV.2019, S. Beshkov & A. Nahirić leg. (Fig. 61). *Euphydryas aurinia* is a species included in Annexes II and IV of the EC Habitat Directive 92/43.

Pyralidae

Loryma egregialis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838) Bulgaria: Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 62); Sakar,

Fig. 63. *Cynaeda superba* ♀. NMK, Gradsko 31.V.2019.

Fig. 64. *Diasemiopsis ramburialis* ♂. AI, Terbunit 25.VIII.2023.

Fig. 65. *Spoladea recurvalis* ♀. MNE, Drume 12.XI.2023.

Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 2 males; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 1 male.

Crambidae

Cynaeda superba (Freyer, 1845) North Macedonia: Tikveš, near Gradsko and Stobi, 662 m, N41°29'08",

Fig. 66. *Antigastra catalaunalis* ♀. BG, Sofia 15.X.2024.

E021°50'44", 31.V.2019, warm sandy slopes with *As-tracantha*, 1 female (Fig. 63). Very rare species in Europe, known from a few localities in Albania and North Macedonia.

Diasemiopsis ramburialis (Duponchel, 1834) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 male (Fig. 64).

Spoladea recurvalis (Fabricius, 1775) Montenegro: Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 female (Fig. 65). New genus and new species for Montenegro. Albania: Këlcyrës Gorge on Aaos River, 10.XI.2023, 1 male and 1 female.

Antigastra catalaunalis (Duponchel, 1833) Serbia: Vidlič Mts, Pirot region, above Krupac Village, Rumenac, 525 m, N43.12068, E022.68643, 29.X.2024, stony steppe-like slopes near forest, 1 male at daytime. Second report for Serbia, known before from Pirot, Mt Vidlič, Crni Vrh summit and from Bela Palanka district, Mt Šljivoviki Vis, above Šljivovik village (Plant et al., 2017); Bulgaria: Sofia, City Center, on a wall, 15.X.2024, S. Beshkov leg., 1 female (Fig. 66). In Bulgaria there are two records for September 1995 from Eastern Rhodopi, Ivaylovgrad region (Goater, 1996; Beshkov & Goater, 2000; Beshkov & Langourov, 2004; Plant, 2016). According to Plant (2016), *Antigastra catalaunalis* is a Mediterranean species associated with dry, usually coastal habitats and the Bulgarian records are surely of immigrants. Similarly, the Serbian record and the record from Sofia also presumably relate to immigrants; moreover, the specimens were collected in habitats that were unusual for them.

Hydriris ornatalis (Duponchel, 1832) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 2 males (Fig. 67) and 1 female; Albania: Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 1 female.

Fig. 67. *Hydrilis ornatalis* ♂. BiH, Jasen Village 14.XI.2023.

Drepanidae

Thyatirinae

Ochropacha duplaris (Linnaeus, 1761) Bulgaria: W. Stara Planina, Gorni Lom – Martinovo, 25.VI.2021, 1 female; Rila Mts, Tiha Rila above Rilski Manastir, 1946 m, N42.1386, E023.4669, 10.VII.2021, ecotone wet meadow with orchids and meadow and *Pinus*, *Abies*, *Betula*, *Salix*, *Verbascum*, *Rumex*, *Chamaecytisus absinthioides*, *Juniperus*, 1 female. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is endangered in Bulgaria – EN B2ab(iii).

Polyploca ridens (Fabricius, 1787) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 1 female.

Drepaninae

Cilix asiatica O. Bang-Haas, 1907 Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024; Albania, Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 female; Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024; Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, above Sladun Village, 18.V.2024, 1 female; NW above Glushnik Village, 02.VI.2023, 1 female.

Geometridae

Orthostixinae

Orthostixis cribraria (Hübner, 1799) Bulgaria: Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024.

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Fig. 68. *Pseudoterpna pruinata* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023, GP.1.18.4.2024.

Fig. 69. *Pseudoterpna pruinata* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023, GP.1./18.4.2024.

Geometrinae

Pseudoterpna pruinata (Hufnagel, 1767) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 68), genitalia checked (Fig. 69).

Comibaena bajularia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male.

Eucrostes indigenata (Villers, 1789) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024.

Phaiogramma etruscaria (Zeller, 1849) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 2 males; Serbia: Straža,

Fig. 70. *Isturgia berytaria* ♂. AL, Ksamil 28.XI.2024.

Fig. 71. *Pachynemia hippocastanaria* ♂. BG, Egrek 5.VI.2024.

09.VI.2024; Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024; Sakar, Oreshnik, 06.V.2024, 1 male.

Ennominae

Odontognophos dumetata (Treitschke, 1827) Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 1 male. Second report for Montenegro. Known before from Maglić Mt, above Mratinje Village (Beshkov, 2017a).

Dicrognophos sartata (Treitschke, 1827) Albania: Progonat, 22.VI.2023, 1 female.

Narraga tessularia (Metzner, 1845) Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 17.VIII.2024, 1 male; Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila, 13.IV.2024, 1 male at light.

Fig. 72. *Apochima flabelaria* ♂. NMK, Dračev Dol 09.III.2024.

Isturgia berytaria (Staudinger, 1892) Albania: Ksamil 28.XI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 70). New species for Albania. In Europe *Isturgia berytaria* is otherwise known only from Greece.

Isturgia arenacearia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 1 male.

Neognopharmia stevenaria (Boisduval, 1840) Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024.

Macaria wauaria (Linnaeus, 1758) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 male. Second report for Montenegro. Previously in Montenegro known only from Durmitor Mts (Rebel & Zerny, 1931).

Pachynemia hippocastanaria (Hübner, 1799) Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 71). In Bulgaria, this species was known only from a single locality above Kosti Village in Strandzha Mts (Beshkov, 2009a). Second report for Bulgaria.

Epione vespertalia (Linnaeus, 1767) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 male.

Apeira syringaria (Linnaeus, 1758) Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024.

Asovia maeoticaria (Alphéraky, 1876) Serbia: Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885m, 07.VIII.2024.

Selenia tetralunaria (Hufnagel, 1767) Bulgaria: Strandzha, Popovi Skali, 09.VII.2024.

Crocallis tusciaria (Borkhausen, 1793) Albania: Ksamil 28.XI.2024, 1 male; Tepelene Region, Drino River, 27.XI.2024, 1 female.

Artiora evonymaria ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2023, 1 female.

Alsophila aescularia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male. A new genus and new species for Albania. The reason why it was not found before is probably its very early flight period.

Apochima flabellaria (Heeger, 1838) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 09.III.2024, 2 males (Fig. 72).

Chondrosoma fiduciaria Anker, 1854 Bulgaria: Sofia Region, above Kostinbrod Town, between Ponor and Bezden villages, 897 m, N42.914313, E023.104652, 24.XI.2023, limestone dry rocky grass-

lands with *Silene*, *Satureja*, *Artemisia alba*, *Crataegus*, *Syringa vulgaris*, *Paeonia tenuifolia*, *Iris*, 1 male (Fig. 73); Ibid, near Ponor Village, 917 m, N42.91524, E023.1287. 20.X.2024, stony slopes with *Artemisia alba* on limestone area, 1 male (Fig. 74). A new genus and a new species for the Balkan Peninsula. *Chondrosoma fiduciaria* is a species included in Annexes II and IV of the EC Habitat Directive 92/43. With this addition, the BG0000322 Dragoman Natura 2000 protected area from EEC 92/43 Habitat Directive (Approved on 12.XII.2008 by the European Commission) takes the leading place among the

Fig. 73. *Chondrosoma fiduciaria* ♂. BG, Ponor 24.XI.2023.

Fig. 74. *Chondrosoma fiduciaria* ♂. BG, Ponor 20.X.2024.

Fig. 75. Ponor, day of the fire, 22.X.2023.

Fig. 76. Collecting spot of *Chondrosoma fiduciaria*, 24.XI.2023.

Natura 2000 Protected areas in Bulgaria for the number of protected Lepidoptera species from Annex II of the Habitat Directive. This site, however, needs strict protection because of threats such as arson, heavy machinery movement, illegal dumps and overgrowth with bushes. The first specimen of this species was found flying in daytime in an area that had been burned recently (22.X.2023, Fig. 75), including the collecting spot (Fig. 76). The following year *Chondrosoma fiduciaria* was found in an unburned area in October. That day we looked for *Ch. fiduciaria* in that area, including the terrains which were burned last year, but without success. *Lignyoptera fumidaria* (Hübner, 1825), another species from Annexes II and IV of the EC Habitat Directive 92/43, well presented before in this area, was not noticed this time. We accept burning as a major and irreversible threat to these two species, of which the females are wingless and have no chance of escaping a fire. The closest localities of *Ch. fiduciaria* are in S Hungary, which suggests that it may also occur in Serbia. A reasons why *Ch. fiduciaria* was not found in the Balkans before may be its late flight period and diurnal activity. The same year, at the very end of October–beginning of November, we were twice in Serbia in suitable similar habitats, close to the border with Bulgaria, to search

for *Chondrosoma fiduciaria*. Visited locations were above Moklište near Bela Palanka, Krupac near Piroto, Gulenovci and Gornji Krivodol near Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod) Town. The research in Serbia is expected to continue in 2025 and ahead.

Aleucis orientalis (Staudinger, 1892) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 1 female; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 2 males (Fig. 77) and 1 female. Rare species in Serbia, reported as new for the country from Trnava near Preševo by Beshkov & Nahirić (2016) and from Starac Mt, Turski Grob (Beshkov, 2017).

Charissa mutilata (Staudinger, 1878) Serbia: Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 78). New species for Serbia. *Charissa mutilata* is a species that for a long time was expected to be found in Serbia, because it is well presented in BG0000322 Dragoman Natura 2000 protected area from Beledie Han to Chepan, where it flies from the late March (23.III.2024, Tri Ushi, 730 m) to the end of August (25.VIII.2015, Chepan, 975 m). For eleven years we looked for this species in Serbia, in habitats similar to these in Bulgaria i.e. Mountain petrophytic steppes 02E1. Relationships with habitat classifications: EUNIS: E1.21 Helleno-Balkan [*Satureja montana*] steppes; PAL. CLASS.:

Fig. 77. *Aleucis orientalis* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar 6.IV.2024.

Fig. 79. *Charissa onustaria* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

Fig. 78. *Charissa mutilata* ♂. SRB, Bačevo 11.VIII.2024.

Fig. 80. *Charissa supinaria* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

34.311 Helleno-Balkan savory steppes; HD 92/43: 62A0 Eastern sub-Mediterranean dry grasslands (*Scorzoneretalia villosae*). In such or similar habitats, we searched at light in: Rtanj Mt above Mužinac Village; in Divna Gorica in Suva Planina; in Šljivovički Vis Mt above Bela Palanka; above Moklište Village near Bela Palanka; near Krupac Village near Pirot; below Crni Vrh in Vidlič Mt above Pirot; above Gulenovci Village in Vidlič Mt; above Gornji Krivodol in Stara Planina; between Bačevo and Dimitrovgrad, in most of the localities several times. We still expect to find it in some of the localities mentioned above. In Europe, *Charissa mutilata* is a very local species, known previously only from Bulgaria – Dragoman Natura 2000 protected area and the vicinity of Assenovgrad Town in the Rhodopi Mts (Beshkov, 2017a, as *Charissa pantheri* (Rebel, 1901)). The first report for Bulgaria

is that of Beshkov (2017a), who wrongly reported it as *Charissa pantheri* due to misidentification. From Greece, it seems also to be erroneously reported (Müller et al., 2019) as a result of misidentification instead of *Charissa peloponnesiaria* Erlacher & Erlacher (2017).

Charissa onustaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 3 males (Fig. 79).

Charissa supinaria (Mann, 1854) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 4 males; Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 1 male, genitalia checked; Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 4 males and 2 females; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 2 males; Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked; Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 1 male; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass 19.V.2023, 5 males, genitalia checked; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 2 males (Fig. 80). Reported as a new

Fig. 81. *Charissa graecaria* ♂. ups SRB, Divna Gorica 1186 m 09.VIII.2024.

Fig. 83. *Menophra berenicidaria* ♂. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

Fig. 82. *Charissa graecaria* ♂. unds SRB, Divna Gorica 1186 m 09.VIII.2024.

Fig. 84. *Menophra berenicidaria*, male genitalia. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023, GP1./23.II.2025.

species for Serbia from the same locality, but from the very beginning of May (Beshkov et al., 2024).

Charissa graecaria (Staudinger, 1871) = *certhiatus* (Rebel & Zerny, 1931) Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 1 male (Figs 81–82). Second locality for Serbia, known before only from Vasilin Vrh from August (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2020; Beshkov et al., 2024). The specimens from Vasilin Vrh in July, reported by Beshkov & Nahirić (2020) as *Charissa graecaria*, belong to another species – *Charissa pullata* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (Beshkov et al., 2024). *Ch. certhiatus* is wrongly mentioned for Montenegro in Beshkov (2009b), not in the article in the same journal and the same year (Beshkov, 2009c), wrongly quoted in Beshkov et al. (2024).

Dyscia raunaria (Freyer, 1851) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 2 females; Maja e Manjolave,

20.VI.2023, 1 female; Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 8 males and 3 females, very small individuals, genitalia checked; Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 4 males; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male and 1 female.

Dyscia innocentaria sicanaria (Oberthür, 1923) Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 24.V.2024, 1 female.

Menophra abruptaria (Thunberg, 1792) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 1 male; Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 male; Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 1 male; Devoli Gorge, near Bratile, 04.V.2022, 1 male; Ersekë County, above Borovë, 21.VII.2022, 1 male.

Menophra japygiaria (O. Costa, 1849) Albania: Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 1 male.

Menophra berenicidaria (Turati, 1924) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 4 males (Fig. 83), gen. prep. 1./23.

Fig. 85. *Eumera regina* ♀. BG, Trun, Krivonoska Mogila 02.IX.2023.

Fig. 88. *Biston rosenbaueri* ♂. AL, Qarr, 10.III.2024.

Fig. 86. *Apocheima hispidaria* ♂. AL, Qarr 10.III.2024.

Fig. 87. *Phigalia pilosaria* ♂. AL, Qarr 10.III.2024.

II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia on glass in Euparal (Fig. 84); Devoli Gorge, near Bratile, 04.V.2022, 4 males and 1 female, genitalia of 1 male checked, in microvial in glycerol. New species for Albania.

Cleorodes lichenaria (Hufnagel, 1767) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1

male; Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male; Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 03.IX.2022, 1 male; Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Oreshnik, 06.V.2024, 2 males.

Eumera regina Staudinger, 1892 Albania: Gjirokaster, between Mal Çajup and Erind, 02.X.2019, 1 male; North Macedonia: Galičica Mts, between Dvata Yavora and Bulgarska Tchuka Top, 1591 m, N40.9903, E020.8563, 17.VIII.2013, 7 males; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male and 2 females (Fig. 85); above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024, 1 male. The reported localities here are the highest in Bulgaria, North Macedonia and Albania, and the earliest and latest flight periods of this species are also reported here.

Odontopera bidentata (Clerck, 1759) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 4 males; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Apocheima hispidaria ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 2 males (Fig. 86). New genus and new species for Albania. The reason why it was not found before is its very early flight period.

Phigalia pilosaria ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male (Fig. 87). New genus and a new species for Albania. The reason why it was not found before is presumably its very early flight period.

Lycia graecarius (Staudinger, 1861) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila, 13.IV.2024, 11 males.

Biston rosenbaueri Müller, 2018 Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male (Fig. 88). New species for Albania. North Macedonia: Dračev Dol,

Fig. 89. *Biston rosenbaueri* ♂. NMK, Dračev Dol, 09.III.2024, GP 1./30.XII.2024.

Fig. 91. *Biston rosenbaueri* male genitalia with everted vesica NMK, Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 09.III.2024, GP. 1./31.XII.2024.

Fig. 90. *Biston rosenbaueri*, male genitalia NMK, Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 09.III.2024, GP 1./31.XII.2024.

Fig. 92. *Biston rosenbaueri*, everted vesica NMK, Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 09.III.2024, GP.1./31.XII.2024.

below Rebre, 09.III.2024, 2 male (Fig. 89), gen. prep. 1./31.XII.2024, S. Beshkov, male genitalia (Fig. 90), male genitalia with everted vesica (Fig. 91) and everted vesica (Fig. 92), Euparal slide. Length of the aedeagus 3.2 mm. New species for North Macedonia. Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 5 males (Fig. 93). New species for Serbia. The report of *Biston achyra* Wehrli, 1936 for Bulgaria by Beshkov (2017) must refer to *Biston rosenbaueri*, a species that was not described at that time.

Agriopis leucophaearia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male. Second report for Albania. The first report dates back more than 100 years from 10 km North of Skodra, March 1916 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931).

Fig. 93. *Biston rosenbaueri* ♂. SRB, Jankov Dol 31.III.2024.

Agriopis budashkini Kostjuk, 2009 Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq,

Fig. 94. *Agriopis budashkini* ♂. AL, Vithkuq 26.XI.2024.

Fig. 96. *Agriopis budashkini* ♂. SRB, G. Krivodol 02.XI.2024.

Fig. 95. *Agriopis budashkini*, male genitalia AL, Vithkuq, 26.XI.2024, GP 1./01.II.2025.

Fig. 97. *Agriopis budashkini* male genitalia. SRB, G. Krivodol 02.XI.2024, GP 1./31.I.2025.

26.XI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 94) in negative temperature in the morning, gen. prep. 1./01.II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia on glass in Euparal (Fig. 95). New species for Albania; Serbia: Stara Planina Mts, above Gornji Krivodol Village, 889 m, N43.1139, E022.9461, dy rocky slopes with *Artemisia alba* and *Pinus nigra*, 02.XI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 96), gen. prep. 1./31.I.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia on glass in Euparal (Fig. 97). Second locality for Serbia, up to now known only from Bela Palanka Distr., Šljivo-vički Vis, above Šljivovik Village (Beshkov, 2017).

Paradarisa consonaria (Hübner, 1799) Serbia: Monastery Rača above Bajina Bašta, 30.IV.2022, 1 female; Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 5 males, genitalia checked (Fig. 98); Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above

Fig. 98. *Paradarisa consonaria* male genital armature SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 3 males (Fig. 99), genitalia checked.

Fig. 99. *Paradarisa consonaria* ♂. SRB, Jankov Dol, 31.III.2024.

Fig. 100. *Ectropis crepuscularia* ♂. SRB, Jankov Dol, 31.III.2024.

Fagivorina arenaria (Hufnagel, 1767) Albania: Ersekë County, above Borovë, 21.VII.2022, 1 male; Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male. These localities are distal points of the distribution of this species in the south and south-west in the Balkan Peninsula.

Nychiodes waltheri Wagner, 1919 Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 11.V.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked; Sakar, above Sladun Village, 18.V.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked.

Nychiodes amygdalaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848) Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 male.

Nychiodes dalmatina Wagner, 1909 Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 male, genitalia checked.

Peribatodes secundaria ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Devoli Gorge, near Bratilo, 04.V.2022, 2 males.

Paraboarmia viertlii (Bohatsch, 18332) Bulgaria: S. Pirin, Hrasna, 30.VI.2023, 2 males.

Paraectropis similaria (Hufnagel, 1767) Serbia: above, Veliki Čukar, 982 m, 03.VII.2021, 1 male; Bulgaria: W Stara Planina Mts, between Kopilovtsi Village and Kopren, 830 m, N43.3336, E022.8668, 22.VI.2022, meadows in mixed *Fagus* forest, 2 males; W Stara Planina Mts, confluence of Penkova Reka and Berkovska Reka rivers, above Berkovitsa Town on the road to Haydushki Vodopadi, 558 m, N43.2233, E023.07596, 21.VI.2022, humid mixed *Fagus* forest in river valley and meadows above, 1 male.

Aethalura punctulata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Monastery Rača above Bajina Bašta 30.IV.2022, 2 females.

Ectropis crepuscularia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1

Fig. 101. *Ectropis crepuscularia* male genital armature SRB, Jankov Dol 31.III.2024.

male; Kruševac Region, Čeljsko jezero near Čelije Village, 295 m, N43.4206, E021.1798, 06.VIII.2024, dark forest near water reservoir, 3 males, genitalia checked; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 13 males (Fig. 100) and 2 females, male genitalia checked (Fig. 101); Bulgaria: W Stara Planina Mts, above Gorni Lom Village, 791 m, N43.4302, E022.7179, 08.IV.2022, river valley with *Fagus*, *Acar*, *Salix*, *Corylus*, etc., 1 male; W Stara Planina Mts, Mladenin Vir above Dalgi Del Village, Berkovitsa district, 534 m, N43.2471, E022.9632, 26.VI.2022, river valley in mixed *Fagus* forest, 2 males, genitalia checked; Lyulin Mts, above Dragichevo, 18.VII.2022, 2 males, genitalia checked.

Sterrhinae

Cleta filacearia (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852) Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, at

Fig. 102. *Cleta filacearia* ♂. AL, Tomori, 16.VI.2024.

Fig. 104. *Idaea mancipiata repagulata* ♂. BG, Kalimok 11.VI.1994 GP 2./20.II.2025.

Fig. 103. *Idaea determinata* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 18.VI.2024.

Fig. 105. *Idaea mancipiata repagulata* male genitalia BG, Kalimok 11.VI.1994 GP 2./20.II.2025.

daytime, 2 males (Fig. 102) and 2 females. In Albania, known only from Mali me Gropa, 1350 m in July (Urbahn, 1966). Second report for Albania; Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 3 males and 1 female; Sakar, near Mramor Village, 05.V.2024, 1 male.

Idaea determinata (Staudinger, 1876) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 103); Bulgaria: S. Pirin, Hrasna, 30.VI.2023, 2 males and 1 female.

Idaea mancipiaria repagulata Prout, 1913 Bulgaria: Danube Plain, “Kalimok” research station near Nova Tchernia Village, Toutrakan district, 23 m, N44.01137, E026.4393, 11.VI.1994, rural fields near marsh area with *Phragmites*, *Typha* and other aquatic vegetation, D. Vassilev leg., 1 male (Fig. 104), gen. prep. 2./20.II.2025. S. Beshkov, male genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 105). New species for the Balkan Peninsula and, respectively, for Bulgaria.

Idaea trigeminata (Haworth, 1809) Albania: Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 1 female

Fig. 106. *Idaea infirmaria* ♀. NMK, Pletvar 5.VII.2024.

Idaea infirmaria Rambur, 1833) North Macedonia: Prilep, Pletvar Pass, 05.VII.2024, 2 females (Fig.

Fig. 107. *Scopula orientalis* ♂. AL Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

Fig. 109. *Scopula orientalis* male genitalia with sternum 8. BG, Shtit, 17.V.2024 GP. 3./09.II.2025.

Fig. 108. *Scopula orientalis* ♂. BG, Shtit 17.V.2024.

Fig. 110. *Scopula immutata* ♂. AL, Kosan 02.VII.2024.

106); Bulgaria: Strandzha Mts, Papiya, 11.VII.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Scopula orientalis (Alphéraky, 1876) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 107). Third report for Albania, known before from Devoli gorge only – Strelcha (Beshkov, 2017) and two spots near Bratilë Village (Beshkov et al., 2024); Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 17.V.2024, 3 males (Fig. 108), gen. prep. 3./09.II.2025, S. Beshkov male genitalia with 8 sternit on glass in euparal (Fig. 109), wingspan 25.2–28.0 mm. Second report and the first georeferenced locality for Bulgaria. Up to now, it was only mentioned and marked for SW Bulgaria in the distribution map in Hausmann (2004), as the source is a specimen in the collection of Jari-Pekka Kaitila (Helsinki, Finland) from S. Pirin near Pirin Village (Jari-Pekka Kaitila, pers. comm. to S. Beshkov, April 2019).

Scopula submutata (Treitschke, 1828) Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 17.VII.2024.

Scopula imitaria (Hübner, 1799) Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 male.

Scopula immutata (Linnaeus, 1758) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 2 males (Fig. 110), gen. preps. 1./18.II.2025 (Fig. 111) and 2./18.II.2025 (Fig. 112), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with sternum A8, Euparal slides. New species for Albania; Bulgaria: Danube Plain, “Kalimok” research station near Nova Cherna Village, Toutrakan district, 23 m, N44.01137, E026.4393, 11.VI.1994, rural fields near marsh area with *Phragmites*, *Typha* and other aquatic vegetation, D. Vassilev leg., 1 male, det. and in coll. S. Beshkov, genitalia, with sternum 8 checked, in microvial in glycerol, aedeagus lost; Ibid, 29.VIII.2005, S. Beshkov leg. at 160 W MVL, 2 males and 2 females.

Scopula flaccidaria (Zeller, 1852) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male; Bulgaria: Atanassovsko Ezero Lake, 30.VII.2022, 2 males (Figs 113–114),

Fig. 111. *Scopula immutata* male genitalia with sternum 8. AL, Kosan 02.VII.2024, GP 1./18.II.2025.

Fig. 112. *Scopula immutata* male genitalia with sternum 8. AL, Kosan 02.VII.2024, GP 2./18.II.2025.

gen. prep. 1./26.II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with sternum 8 on glass in euparal (Fig. 115); Silvercoast, "Bukvite" above Balchik, 06.IX.2022, 2 males.

Rhodostrophia calabra (Petagna 1787) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024.

Larentiinae

Schistostege decussata dinarica (Schawrda, 1913) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 116); Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024.

Fig. 113. *Scopula flaccidaria* ♂. BG, Atanasovsko Ezero 30.VII.2022.

Fig. 114. *Scopula flaccidaria* ♂. BG, Atanasovsko Ezero 30.VII.2022, GP 1./26.II.2025.

Fig. 115. *Scopula flaccidaria* male genitalia with sternum 8. BG, Atanasovsko Ezero 30.VII.2022, GP 1./26.II.2025.

Fig. 116. *Schistostege decussata dinarica* ♂. Maja Ahishtes Geges 18.VI.2024.

Fig. 119. *Chesias rufata pinkeri* ♂. AL, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023.

Fig. 117. *Chesias rufata rufata* ♂. AL, Qarr, 10.III.2024.

Fig. 120. *Chesias rufata pinkeri* ♂. AL, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023.

Fig. 118. *Chesias rufata rufata* ♀. SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

Chesias rufata rufata (Fabricius, 1775) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male (Fig. 117); Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 female (Fig. 118). *Chesias rufata rufata* (Fabricius, 1775) was reported and illustrated as new for Albania from Bulqizë Town area (Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021). Second report for Albania.

Chesias rufata pinkeri Schawerda, 1939 Albania: Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023 (Figs 119–120). New subspecies for Albania.

Celonoptera mirificaria paradoxaria (Staudinger, 1862) Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024; Progonat, 22.VI.2023, 1 male; Tomori Mts, above Korita Village, 17.VI.2024, 6 males (Fig. 121). In Albania *C. mirificaria paradoxaria* was known from a single specimen from Gjirokastër County: Kolonjë (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018). Second report for Albania.

Acasis viretata (Hübner, 1799) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 2 males.

Euchoeca nebulata (Scopoli, 1763) Serbia: Pčinja River Valley, Vražji Kamen near Trgovište, 10.VII.2016, 2 males. In Serbia, *Euchoeca nebulata* has been reported from Fruška Gora (Stojanovic, Čurčić & Brajkovic, 2010; Stojanovic, 2012) and Domena in Timočka Krajina (Tomić, 2002).

Fig. 121. *Celonoptera mirificaria paradoxaria* ♂. AL, Tomori, above Korita 17.VI.2024.

Fig. 122. *Scotopteryx ignorata* ♀. MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024, GP 1./08.II.2025.

Scotopteryx coarctaria ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 2 males.

Scotopteryx vicinaria (Duponchel, 1830) Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024.

Scotopteryx ignorata Huemer & Hausmann, 1998 Albania: Qafa e Pashkasheshit above Iba, 21.V.2023, 1 female, genitalia checked, in microvial in glycerol; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 1 female, genitalia checked, in microvial in glycerol. In Albania known from Krushovë above Voskopojë (Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021) and from Guri i Kamjes (Beshkov et al., 2024). Third report for Albania; Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 122), gen. prep. 1./08.II.2025, S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 123). Reported as a new species for Montenegro from almost the same locality, but in August (Beshkov et al., 2024); Bulgaria: NW above Glushnik Village, 02.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 124). The last locality is the

Fig. 123. *Scotopteryx ignorata* female genitalia. MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024, GP 1./08.II.2025.

Fig. 124. *Scotopteryx ignorata* ♂. BG, Glushnik, 02.VI.2023.

lowest and the most eastern locality for this species yet reported.

Fig. 125. *Scotopteryx olympia* ♂. MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024, GP 1./9.II.2025.

Fig. 127. *Scotopteryx olympia* ♂. SRB, Karaula 30.VI.2024.

Fig. 126. *Scotopteryx olympia* male genitalia. MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024, GP 1./9.II.2025.

Fig. 128. *Xanthorhoe oxybiata* ♀. BG, Sheynovets 07.X.2022.

Scotopteryx olympia Rezbanyai-Reser, 2003 Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 5 males (Fig. 125), gen. prep. 1./09.II.2025, genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 126). Reported from near the same locality, but in August (Beshkov et al., 2024); Serbia: Jadovnik Mts, Mali Jadovnik, 1512 m, N43.2997, E019.7778, 03.VII.2019, limestone area with *Juniperus communis* near coniferous forest, 3 males, genitalia of 1 male checked; Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 10 males (Fig. 127) and 2 females. New species for Serbia.

Phibalapteryx virgata (Hufnagel, 1767) Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 1 male. In Serbia, *Phibalapteryx virgata* is known from Deliblatska Peščara and Sombor (Tomić, 2002); Bulgaria: Slivnitsa, above Aldomirovsko Blato, 11.V.2024, 1 male and 1 female at daytime.

Xanthorhoe oxybiata (Millière, 1872) Bulgaria: Meandrite na Byala Reka, 06.X.2022, 1 male; Sheynovets above Mezek, 07.X.2022, 3 females (Fig. 128); E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 03.IX.2022, 1 female; Ibid, 05.X.2022, 2 males.

Catarhoe putridaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 20.VII.2022, 1 female; Serbia: Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac Village, 1030 m, N43.7636, E021.8989 02.VII.2021, limestone slopes and dolines with *Prunus spinosa*, *Syringa vulgaris*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Quercus*, *Artemisia alba*, etc. 1 male, genitalia checked; Šljivovički Vis, 21.VI.2017, 1

Fig. 129. *Euphyia adumbraria* ♀. GR, Peristera 14.V.2016, GP 2./5.III.2025.

Fig. 131. *Euphyia adumbraria* ♂. SRB, Karaula 30.VI.2024.

Fig. 130. *Euphyia adumbraria* female genitalia. GR, Peristera 14.V.2016, GP 2./5.III.2025.

male, genitalia checked; Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 1 male.

Catarhoe permixtaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852)
Serbia: Pčinja River Valley, Vražji Kamen near Trgovište, 22.VI.2017, 2 males, genitalia checked; Bulgaria: Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village, 14.VI.2023, 1 male.

Catarhoe rubidata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 05.VI.202, 1 female.

Camptogramma scripturata poliata (Schawerda, 1913) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 female.

Euphyia adumbraria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852)
Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male, genitalia checked, in microvial in glycerol. In Albania known only from Munela Mt (Beshkov & Nahirnić 2020a). Second report for Albania; Greece: Peloponnesos, Chelmos Mts, Kalavrita region, above Peristera 1294 m, N38°01'37", E022°14'25", 14.V.2016, submaquis, *Quercus coccifera* on rocky area, 1 female (Fig. 129), gen. prep. 2./05.III.2025, S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 130). New species for Peloponnesos and the southernmost locality of the species; Serbia: Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 131); Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 1 male and 1 female. In Serbia, this species is known only from Savina Voda near Jabuka Pass (Beshkov, 2020; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020) and from this locality (Divna Gocica) at the very end of June (Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Fig. 132. *Euphyia frustata* ♀. MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024, GP 2./09.II.2025.

Fig. 134. *Spargania luctuata* ♂. GR, Vigla 12.VI.2024.

Fig. 133. *Euphyia frustata* female genitalia MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024, GP 2./09.II.2025.

Euphyia frustata (Treitschke, 1828) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 132), gen. prep. 2./09.II.2025, S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 133). This specimen, with its genitalia, is illustrated here for comparison with *Euphyia adumbraria*.

Larentia clavaria (Haworth, 1809) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2023, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 13.X.2024, 1 male.

Spargania luctuata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 134). New genus and new species for Greece. This is also the southernmost locality of this Holarctic species in its range, or at least in Europe. Recently, *S. luctuata* was reported from southern North Macedonia, Baba Mt (Beshkov et al., 2024).

Hydriomena furcata (Thunberg, 1784) Serbia: Četanska Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 2 males; Bulgaria: Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets, 21.VII.2024, 3 males; S Pirin – Alibotoush Mts, above Petrovo, 29.VI.2023, 1 male, genitalia checked; Alibotoush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 2 males; Rila Mts, below Yakorudski Ezera lakes, 2155 m, N42.1014, E023.5999, 22.VII.2024, subalpine slopes above stream, 3 males, genitalia checked.

Thera vetustata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) = *stragulata* (Hübner, 1809) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Bulgaria: W. Rhodopi Mts, above Trigrad Gorge, 02.IX.2022, 1 male and 1 female.

Thera obeliscata (Hübner, 1787) Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 male.

Fig. 135. *Colostygia olivata* ♀. AL, Theth 15.VIII.2018, GP 1./5.III.2025.

Fig. 137. *Colostygia wolfschlaegerae* ♀. AL, Vithkuq 22.IX.2024, GP 1./6.II.2025.

Fig. 136. *Colostygia olivata* female genitalia AL, Theth 15.VIII.2018, GP 1./5.III.2025.

Fig. 138. *Colostygia wolfschlaegerae* female genitalia. AL, Vithkuq 22.IX.2024, GP 1./6.II.2025.

Electrophaes corylata (Thunberg, 1792) Serbia: Straža, 09.VI.2024, 1 female. Reported for Serbia from Užice Area (Dodok, 2006) and Fruška Gora (Stojanović et al., 2010, Stojanović, 2012). Third locality for Serbia.

Dysstroma truncata (Hufnagel, 1767) Serbia: Suva Planina above Bela Palanka, 06.IX.2024, 1 male.

Colostygia olivata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Prokletije Mts, Theth, 817 m, N42.4133, E019.7602, 15.VIII.2018, river valley

with *Corylus*, *Salix*, *Sorbus*, *Carpinus*, *Acer*; meadows, 1 female (Fig. 135), gen. prep. 1./05. III.2025, S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 136). A species proven to be part of the Balkan fauna. In Hausmann & Viidalepp (2012), for the Balkan Peninsula it is marked only for northern Croatia. A new species for Albania.

Colostygia wolfschlaegerae (Pinker, 1953) Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 female (Fig. 137), gen. prep.

Fig. 139. *Colostygia wolfschlaegerae* ♂. AL, Lin 24.IX.2024, GP 2./6.II.2025.

Fig. 141. *Colostygia sericeata* ♂. BiH, Jasen, 14.XI.2023, GP 1./30.XII.2024.

Fig. 140. *Colostygia wolfschlaegerae* male genitalia. AL, Lin 24.IX.2024, GP 2./6.II.2025.

Fig. 142. *Colostygia sericeata* male genitalia. BiH, Jasen, 14.XI.2023, GP 1./30.XII.2024.

1./06.II.2025, S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glas in euparal (Fig. 138); Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 male (Fig. 139), gen. prep. 2./06.II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 140). A new species for Albania.

Colostygia sericeata (Schwingenschuss, 1926) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 3 males (Fig. 141), gen. prep. 1./30.XII.2024, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with abdomen on glass in Euparal (Fig. 142). New species for Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Philereme transversata (Hufnagel, 1767) Albania: above Kruja, 1134 m, N41.5153, E019.8039, 18.VII.2018, limestone rocks and *Pinus* trees; Albania, Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 1 male; Albania, Gjirokaster, between Mal Çajup and Erind, 07.VI.2018.

Pareulype berberata berberata ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near

Fig. 143. *Pareulype berberata* ♀. MNE, Pirlitor 01.VII.2024.

Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 143). New species for Montenegro and for the SW Balkan Peninsula.

Horisme calligraphata (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1

Fig. 144. *Perizoma flavosparsata uniformata* ♂. SRB, Izvor 09.IX.2023.

Fig. 146. *Perizoma flavofasciata* ♂. NMK, Dračev Dol 11.VI.2024.

Fig. 145. *Perizoma flavosparsata uniformata* ♀. SRB, Izvor 09.IX.2023.

Fig. 147. *Perizoma obsoletata* ♀. SRB, Golija 22.VIII.2023 GP 1./16.II.2025.

male; Albania: Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 1 female; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 female; Bulgaria: S. Pirin – Alibotoush Mts, above Petrovo, 29.VI.2023, 1 female.

Perizoma flavosparsata uniformata Mentzer, 1974 Serbia: Bosilegrad, above Izvor Village, 1039 m, N42.5083, E022.5229, 09.IX.2023, slopes with *Quercus*, *Viburnum*, *Cornus mas*, *Crataegus*, orchards, etc. 3 males (Fig. 144) and 3 females (Fig. 145). New species for Serbia. This locality is close to the border with Bulgaria, and we expect *P. flavosparsata uniformata* to be found in Bulgaria. The range of *P. flavosparsata uniformata* is restricted to North Macedonia: Type locality Vodno near Skopje and Derven Pass [Prisad] near Prilep Town (von Mentzer, 1981) and Greece (Mironov, 2003).

Perizoma flavofasciata (Thunberg, 1792) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 146).

Perizoma obsoletata (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838) Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 female (Fig. 147), gen. prep. 1./16.II.2025, S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal (Fig. 148). According to Müller et al. (2019), all populations from the Balkan Peninsula belong to *Perizoma juracolaria* (Wehrli, 1919). In Montenegro, however, both these species are surely proven to occur (Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021). Now, both species are proven in Serbia as well. A new species for Serbia.

Eupithecia venosata (Fabricius, 1787) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 28.V.2023, 1 male; Prespa Lake, near Gilloboçeni Village, 18.V.2023, 2 males (Fig. 149).

Fig. 148. *Perizoma obsoletata* female genitalia. SRB, Golia 22.VIII.2023 GP 1./16.II.2025.

Fig. 149. *Eupithecia venosata* ♂. AL, Gllboçeni, 18.V.2022.

Fig. 150. *Eupithecia extremata* ♂. AL, Tomori, above Korita 17.VI.2024.

Fig. 151. *Eupithecia ochridara* ♂. AL, Guri i Kamnjes 20.V.2023, GP 1./16.I.2025.

Fig. 152. *Eupithecia ochridara* male genitalia with sternum 8. AL, Guti i Kamnjes 20.V.2023, GP 1./16.I.2025.

Eupithecia extremata (Fabricius, 1787) Albania: Tomori Mts, above Korita Village, 17.VI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 150). New species for Albania.

Eupithecia ochridata Schütze & Pinker, 1968 Albania: Pogradec, Guri i Kamnjes, 20.V.2023, 1 male

(Fig. 151), gen. prep. 1./16.I.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with sternum 8 on glass in Euparal (Fig. 152). New species for Albania.

Eupithecia graphata graphata (Treitschke, 1828) North Macedonia: Prilep Region, Babuna

Fig. 153. *Eupithecia graphata graphata* ♂. NMK, Pletvar 02.VI.2018, GP. 1./20.III.2019.

Fig. 155. *Eupithecia graphata olympica* ♂. AL, Tomori 16.VI.2024.

Fig. 154. *Eupithecia graphata graphata* male genitalia. NMK, Pletvar, 02.VI.2018, GP. 1./20.III.2019.

Fig. 156. *Eupithecia graphata olympica* ♂. AL, Tomori 16.VI.2024, GP 2./16.I.2025.

Planina, Pletvar Pass, 989 m, N41.3683; E021.6613, 02.VI.2018, S. Beshkov, A. Nahirnić, C. Plant, A. King & P. Jakšić leg., 1 male (Fig. 153), gen. prep. 1./20.III.2019, S. Beshkov, male genitalia on glass in euparal, 8 sternite lost (Fig. 154). This specimen (wingspan 16 mm) in size and appearance also resembles *Eupithecia riparia* Herrich-Schäffer, 1851, but the genitalia of both these taxa are identical, and the diagnostic sternum 8 is lost. It does, however, differ in appearance and size from *Eupithecia graphata olympica*, also illustrated below (Fig. 155).

Eupithecia graphata olympica Tuleschkov, 1951 Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 5 males (Fig. 155), gen. prep. 2./16.I.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with sternum 8 on glass in Euparal (Fig. 156). For comparison, the lectotype of *Eupithecia graphata olympica*

Fig. 157. *Eupithecia graphata olympica* ♂. Lectotypus. GR, Olymp, 22.VII.1937.

Tuleschkov from the collection NMNHS is also illustrated here (Fig. 157). New species for Albania.

Fig. 158. *Eupithecia insigniata* ♀. SRB, Rtanj 02.V.2022.

Fig. 160. *Eupithecia gratiosata* ♀. BG, Sladun 02.VI.2024.

Fig. 159. *Eupithecia insigniata* ♂. SRB, Bačevo, 30.III.2024.

Fig. 161. *Poecilocampa alpina* ♂. BiH, Mrgudići-Brda, 15.XI.2023.

Eupithecia breviculata (Donzel, 1837) Albania: Lushnja, above Ardenica, 06.V.2022, 1 male; Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 1 female; Serbia: Straža, 09.VI.2024.

Eupithecia insigniata (Hübner, 1790) Albania: Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023, 1 male; Serbia: Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 07.VIII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 158); Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 30.III.2024, 2 males (Fig. 159); Bulgaria: Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila, 13.IV.2024, 1 female.

Eupithecia gueneata Millière, 1862 Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 2 males and 1 female; Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 2 males.

Eupithecia gratiosata Herrich-Schäffer, 1861 Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 3 males and 2 females (Fig. 160). The first, and only, report for *Eupithecia gratiosata* for Bulgaria was that of Levy (1968) a long time ago for Slanchev Bryag near Nese-

bar [South Black Sea Coast]. Second report for Bulgaria. Without any doubt, the locality in Slanchev Bryag has been completely destroyed because of re-development of the infrastructure of this resort, which is the biggest one on the Black Sea Coast of Bulgaria.

Lasiocampidae

Poecilocampa alpina canensis (Millière, 1876) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Tovarnica Mt, near Mrgudići – Brda 15.XI.2023, 2 males (Fig. 161); Albania: Prrenjas – Pogradec, near Qafa Kotodeshit, 07.XI.2023, 2 males and 2 females; Prespa Lake, near Glloboçeni Village, 05-06.XI.2023, 1 male.

Poecilocampa populi (Linnaeus, 1758) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Višegrad, Jegrlići, 16.XI.2023, 1 male.

Trichiura crataegi (Linnaeus, 1758) Montenegro: Rožaje, Vrelo Ibra, 23.VIII.2023, 2 males, genitalia checked; Albania: Kukës County, W of Ploshtan,

26.VIII.2023, 1 male, genitalia checked; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 3 males, genitalia checked.

Malacosoma franconicum ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlahi, 25.V.2024, 1 female, not collected. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is endangered in Bulgaria – EN B2ab(iii).

Eriogaster catax (Linnaeus, 1758) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.III.2023, 1 female; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila, 14.IV.2024, larvae on *Pyrus*, 2 females emerged in Sofia on 18.IX.2024. This species is new for Golo Bardo Mt, part of which is also a Natura 2000 Protected Area – BG0001375 Ostritsa. The locality for *E. catax*, however, is about 0.8 km out of the protected area, but without any doubt this species also inhabits the Natura 2000 site; Sofia Region, Kostinbrod Municipality, near Ponor Village, 894 m, N42.9154, E023.1529, 28.IV.2024, caterpillars on *Pyrus*. This locality is in the BG0000322 Dragoman Natura 2000 protected area, from where *Eriogaster catax* is already known; Bulgaria, Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 1 male and 1 female at light. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is vulnerable in Bulgaria – VU B2ab(iii). *Eriogaster catax* is included in Anexes II and IV of the EC Habitat Directive 92/43. *Eriogaster catax* is a new species for BG0000212 Sakar Natura 2000 Protected area and has to be added to the Natura 2000 Standard Data Form for this site.

Eriogaster rimicola ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 2 females; Second report for Bosnia and Herzegovina, known before from Uskoplje, Grbov Dolac (Koren & Martinović, 2020); Montenegro: Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 male.

Lasiocampa quercus (Linnaeus, 1758) Serbia: Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 07.VIII.2024, 2 females. This is an unusually late flight period; Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt, above Chuypetlyovo on the ground road to Yarlovo, near Zaslon Smilyo, 1354 m, N42.4946, E023.24397, 25.VII.2024, meadows in *Fagus*-coniferous forest on sandy soil, 1 male.

Macrothylacia rubi (Linnaeus, 1758) Serbia: Četanica Mt, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male at light. The flight period is unusually late.

Lemoniidae

Lemonia taraxaci (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 1 male; Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 male.

Lemonia strigata Antoshin & Zolotuhin, 2011 Albania: Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 2 males and 2 females; Këlcyrës Gorge on Aaos River, 10.XI.2023, 2 males; Gjirokaster, between Mal Çajup and Erind, 02.X.2019, 2 males and 1 female; Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 2 males; Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 5 males and 1 female; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 2 males and 2 females; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 21.IX.2024, 3 males; North Macedonia: Suva Gora Mts, Gostivar Region, below Korito Village, 1091 m, N41.8236, E020.9966, 26.IX.2016, dry slopes with *Artemisia* and *Eryngium*, 2 males; Bulgaria: Pirin Mts, Vlahi Village, 556 m, N41.7404, E023.2293, 26.X.2024, rocky gorge with *Pallurus*, *Pistacia*, *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. oxycedrus*, *Quercus* etc., 1 male; S. Pirin – Alibotush, Izvora above Petrovo Village, 643 m, N41.41613, E023.55099, 29.X.2019, spring in *Platanus-Alnus* near *Fagus* forest and open slopes with *Juniperis* and mixed *Carpinus* forest above, 2 males. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016), this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is vulnerable in Bulgaria – VU B2ab(iii). In Bulgaria, all localities of *Lemonia strigata* are in SW Bulgaria, Struma Valley, and the slopes of the mountains around, and with doubt for the Sliven area in E Bulgaria (Hristova & Beshkov, 2016).

Endromidae

Endromis versicolora (Linnaeus, 1758) Serbia: Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 30.III.2024, 2 males; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 1 male.

Saturniidae

Antheraea yamamai Guérin-Ménéville, 1861 Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 male.

Saturnia spini (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) Bulgaria: Dragoman-Slivnitsa, Tri Ushi, above

Fig. 162. *Neopterodonta gorgoniades* ♂. BG, Ilinden, 14.VI.2023.

Fig. 164. *Drymonia velitaris* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

Fig. 163. *Hyppotion celerio* ♂. AL, Gjorm, 03.VII.2024.

Aldomirovsko Blato Swamp, Slivnitsa surroundings, 730 m, N42.8946, E023.0161, 23.III.2024, limestone slopes with *Adonis vernalis*, *Artemisia alba*, *Iris*, *Quercus* spp., 2 males.

Agria tau (Linnaeus, 1758) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Sphingidae

Dolbina elegans A. Bang-Haas, 1913 Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 08.VII.2024, 1 male.

Hemaris fuciformis (Linnaeus, 1758) Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 1 male.

Hyles vespertilio (Esper, 1780) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 2 males; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 17.VIII.2024, 1 male. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016), this species, according to

the criteria of IUCN, is vulnerable in Bulgaria – VU B2ab(iii).

Rethera komarovi drilon Rebel & Zerny, 1931 Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 specimen. New species for the Mesta Valley. *Rethera komarovi* was known in Bulgaria from Kresna Gorge, Alibotoush Mts, and from some more localities in Eastern Rhodopi between Komuniga and Meden Buk villages in the valleys of Arda and Byala Reka rivers (Beshkov & Langourov, 2004; Hristova & Beshkov, 2016; Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021). According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016), *R. komarovi* is Vulnerable (IUCN category VU B2ab(iii)) in Bulgaria.

Neopterodonta gorgoniades (Hübner, [1819]) Bulgaria: Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village, 14.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 162). In Bulgaria, this species was known only from a remote part of the country – the Northern Black Sea Coast between Balchik Town and Cape Kaliakra (Beshkov, 1990; Beshkov, Nahirić-Beshkova & Jakšić, 2024). According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016), this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is critically endangered in Bulgaria – CR B2ab(iii).

Hyppotion celerio (Linnaeus, 1758) Albania: Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 163). Second report for Albania, known before from Tomori Mts, Abaz Aliu Top, 2379 m (Beshkov et al., 2020).

Noctuoidea

Notodontidae

Drymonia velitaris (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 164). New

species for Albania; Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male; Bela Palanka Municipality, Šljivovički Vis Mt, above Šljivovik Village, 1043 m, N43.1519, E022.3848, 01.VII.2021, *Artemisia alba*, limestone meadows 1 male; Bulgaria: W Stara Planina, Gorni Lom – Martinovo, 25.VI.2021, 1 male and 1 female. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is endangered in Bulgaria – EN B2ab(iii).

Drymonia querna ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Ersekë County, above Borovë, 21.VII.2022, 1 female.

Peridea korbi (Rebel, 1918) Bulgaria: NW above Glushnik Village, 02.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 165). This is the most northeastern locality of this species in Bulgaria. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is vulnerable in Bulgaria – VU B2ab(iii).

Ptilophora plumigera ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 1 male; Tovarnica Mt, near Mrgudići – Brda 15.XI.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Višegrad, Jegrlići, 16.XI.2023; Montenegro: Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 13.XI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 166). A new genus and new species for Montenegro; Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 26.XI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 167) and 1 female (Fig. 168) in negative temperature in the morning. Second locality for Albania, previously known from Liqeni Prespa e vogel, near Tren Village (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020a).

Rhegmatophila alpina osmana Friedel, 1967 Bulgaria: Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village, 14.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 169); E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is endangered in Bulgaria – EN B2ab(iii).

Fig. 165. *Peridea korbi* ♂. BG, Glushnik 02.VI.2023.

Fig. 166. *Ptilophora plumigera* ♂. MNE, Povija, 13.XI.2023.

Fig. 167. *Ptilophora plumigera* ♂. AL, above Vithkuq, 26.XI.2024.

Fig. 168. *Ptilophora plumigera* ♀. AL, above Vithkuq, 26.XI.2024.

Fig. 169. *Rhegmatophila alpina osmana* ♂. BG, Ilinden, 14.VI.2023.

Fig. 170. *Nola confusalis* ♂. AL, Guri i Kamjes 20.V.2023, GP 3./18.II.2025.

Nola confusalis (Herrich-Schäfferr, 1847)
Albania: Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023, 1 male (Fig. 170), gen. prep. 3./18.II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with 8th abdominal segment on glass in Euparal (Fig. 171). In Albania, *N. confusalis* was known only from Korab (Rebel & Zerny, 1931). Second report for Albania; Bulgaria: W Stara Planina Mts, Zhenska Reka river above Berkovitsa Town, 523 m, N43.2332, E23.08368, 15.IV.2022, meadow near *Fagus* forest in river valley, 1 female.

Fig. 171. *Nola confusalis* male genitalia with eight abdominal segment. AL, Guri i Kamjes 20.V.2023, GP 3./18.II.2025.

Paradrymonia vittata streckfussi (Honrath, 1892)
Serbia: Straža, 09.VI.2024, 2 males.

Thaumetopoea solitaria (Freyer, 1838) Bulgaria:
E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 03.IX.2022, 1 male. According to Hristova & Beshkov (2016) this species, according to the criteria of IUCN, is vulnerable in Bulgaria – VU B2ab(iii).

Nolidae

Nolinae

Nola togatulis (Hübner, 1796) Albania: Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 female.

Meganola albula ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male.

Nola cicatricalis (Treitschke, 1835) Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 2 males.

Fig. 172. *Nola chlamitulalis* ♂. AL, Maja Achishtes Geges 18.VI.2024, GP 4./18.II.2025.

Nola chlamitulalis (Hübner, [1813]) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 172), gen. prep. 4./18.II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with 8th abdominal segment (Fig. 173).

Fig. 173. *Nola chlamitulalis* male genitalia with eight abdominal segment. AL, Maja Achishtes Geges 18.VI.2024, GP 4./18.II.2025.

Fig. 174. *Ocneria ledereri* ♂. BG, Kresna – Vlahi 25.V.2024.

Chloephorinae

Nycteola siculana (Fuchs, 1899) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 female.

Erebidae

Lymantriinae

Ocneria ledereri (Millière, 1868) Bulgaria: Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlahi, 25.V.2024, 1 male (Fig. 174); Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, 1 female. In this species usually only females are collected, and males are exceptions.

Ocneria detrita (Esper, [1785]) Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 1 male; Prrenjas – Pogradec, near Qafa Kotodeshit,

23.VII.2022, 2 males and 4 females; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 20.VII.2022, 1 male; Bulgaria: Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village, 14.VI.2023, 1 male; Sakar Mt, Kostur Village NE, 42.001794, E26.296842, 700 m, 04.VI.2024, during daytime.

Ocneria terebinthi (Lederer, 1838) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Šljivovički Vis, 21.VI.2017, 1 male; Ibid, 1043 m, N43.1519, E022.3848, 01.VII.2021, 1 male.

Orgyia antiqua (Linnaeus, 1758) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 1 male. In Albania previously known only from Tirana (The Botanical Garden) (Misja, 1990). Second report for Albania.

Arctiinae

Diaphora luctuosa (Geyer, [1831]) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 1 male; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male; Bela Palanka, above Moklište, 07.IV.2024, 1 male.

Watsonarctia deserta (Bartel, 1902) Albania: Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male; Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Četanska Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male.

Phragmatobia placida (Frivaldszky, 1835) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 3 males.

Chelis maculosa ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male.

Chelis maculosa honesta (Tauscher, 1806) = *mannerheimi* Duponchel, 1936 Bulgaria: Danube Plain, Toutrakan district, “Mogilata” near “Kalimok” research station near Nova Cherna Village, 29 m, N44.0051, E026.4499, 29.VIII.2005, steppe area with rural fields and wetlands around, S. Beshkov leg. at 15 W actinic light trap, 25 males (Figs 175–176); Silvercoast, “Bukvite” above Balchik, 19.VIII.2022, 1 male; N Black Sea Coast, above Balchik Town, Bukvite – military airport, 187 m, N43.4093, E028.1785, 03.VIII.2022, 3 males; Black Sea Coast, Silvercoast, between Topola and Bozhurets villages, 39 m, N43°24'40”, E028°16'04”, 16.VI.2014, sandy slopes in steppe area with *Artemisia*, etc. S. Beshkov & S. Abadjiev leg., 1 male; Dobrogea, near Loznitsa Village, 115 m, N43.97208, E27.92707, 22.VIII.2012, steppe area, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg., 2 males; Dobrogea, near Rossen Village, near Yazovir Dryan, 182 m, N43°52'12”,

Fig. 175. *Chelis maculosa honesta* ♂. BG Kalimok, Mogilata 29.VIII.2005, BC SB Lep0325.

Fig. 176. *Chelis maculosa honesta* ♂. BG Kalimok, Mogilata 29.VIII.2005.

Fig. 177. *Chelis maculosa honesta* ♂. BG, Suhata Reka Vojnovo 24.VII.2010.

E027°57'27", 02.V.2012, steppe area, ruderal, rocks, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg., 2 males; Dobrogea, near Rosen Village, 165 m, N43.8586, E027.9605, 10.VIII.2022, 2 males; Ibid, 150 m, N43°51'23", E027°57'39", 23.VII.2010, 8 males, S. Beshkov leg.; Dobrogea, Kraishite Village, 140 m, N43°51'40", E027°57'28", 25.VIII.2011, stony slopes with *Artemisia*, steppe vegetation in small river valley, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg., 13 males; Suhata Reka above Kapitan Dimitrovo Village, 11.VIII.2022, 1 male; Dobrogea, Souhata Reka river, "Divi Boy" near

Golesh Village, 100 m, 06.VI.1999, between meadow and *Acer-Carpinus-Quercus* forest and a limestone area, S. Beshkov, S. Abadjiev & M. Langourov leg., 1 male; Dobrogea, Souhata Reka, below Kranovo Village, Kaynardzha district, 76 m, N44°00'54", E027°39'32", 18.V.2010, *Quercus-Carpinus* forest and open limestone area, S. Beshkov, C. Plant & B. Benedek leg., 1 male; Dobrogea, Suhata Reka, between Vojnovo and Strelkovo villages, 120 m, N43°57'35", E027°25'58", 24.VII.2010, steppe area with *Artemisia*, river with *Salix*, S. Beshkov leg., 1 male (Fig. 177); Dobrogea, Kachamaka Place near Bezhanovo Village, 78 m, N43°42'45", E028°24'19", 23.VIII.2011, steppe area with *Artemisia alba*, etc. S. Beshkov, M. Beshkova, P. and A. Gyulai leg., 12 males; Dobrogea, Snyagovo near Kardam, 166 m, N43°45'23", E028°04'35", 24.VIII.2011, pasture, gardens, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg., 5 males; Eastern Stara Planina Mts, above Dropla Village, Daskotna district, 234 m, N42°54'45", E027°12'44", 21.VIII.2011, near *Quercus* forest and meadows around, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg. In Bulgaria *Ch. maculosa honesta* is proved to occur NE of the line Nova Cherna near Tutrakan – Balchik (Dobrogea, Eastern part of Danube Plain, N. Black Sea Coast) and the lower, most eastern part E. Stara Planina Mts (Daskotna district). Habitat is a steppe or ruderal-steppe area.

Arctia festiva (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 3 males; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 09.III.2024, 2 males; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila, 13.IV.2024, 2 males.

Arctia flavia (Fuessly, 1779) Bulgaria: Rila, above Karagyol reservoir below Kalin Peak, 25.VII.2023, 1 male; Ibid, below Kalin Peak, 2554 m, N42.1799, E023.2615, 25.VII.2023.

Euplagia quadripunctaria (Poda, 1761) Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 34 specimens at 2 light traps; Suva Planina, above Bela Palanka Town, 1064 m, N43.1984, E022.2549, 09.VIII.2024, ecotone of *Fagus* forest with *Corylis colurna* and road with *Artemisia alba* on limestone ground, 160W MVL lamp and 9W LED 368nm lamp, 30 specimens. *Euplagia quadripunctaria* is a priority species, included in Annexes II and IV of the EC Habitat Directive 92/43.

Cymbalophora rivularis (Ménétriés, 1832) Bulgaria: Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 3 males (Fig. 178). In Bulgaria *C.*

Fig. 178. *Cymbalophora rivularis* ♂. BG, Mihalich 11.X.2024.

Fig. 181. *Macrochilo cribrumalis* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Fig. 179. *Thumatha senex* ♂. AL, Ptespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Fig. 180. *Pelosia obtusa* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

rivularis is known from Sakar Mt, Dripchevo Village (Ganev & Kiriakov 1986) and from Shumen (Beshkov et al. 2024).

Utetheisa pulchella (Linnaeus, 1758) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 1 female; Albania: Këlcyrës Gorge on Aaos River, 10.XI.2023, 1 male; Benjë-Novoselë near Petran, 09.XI.2023, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 male.

Thumatha senex (Hübner, [1808]) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 males and 4 females (Fig. 179). New genus and new species for Albania; Bulgaria: N. Black Sea Coast, Shabla Lake,

near the Residence, 19 m, N43.5661, E028.5786, 06.VIII.2022, *Elaeagnus*, garden, open area near lake with aquatic vegetation, 1 male.

Pelosia obtusa (Herrich-Schaffer, [1852]) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 180). New species for Albania; Bulgaria: Atanassovsko Ezero Lake, 09.IX.2014, S. Beshkov & S. Abadjiev leg., 1 male.

Eilema griseola (Hübner, [1808]) Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodopi Mts, Kirkovo Municipality, above Shumnatitsa Village, 572 m, N41°15'53", E025°21'17", 14.VII.2015, *Fagus-Quercus-Carpinus* forest, river valley with *Alnus*, S. Beshkov, B. Zlatkov & C. Plant leg., genitalia of 1 male checked. *Eilema griseola* is a very rare species in Bulgaria, and perhaps some of the reported localities are a result of misidentification instead of *Eilema depressa* (Esper, [1787]).

Eilema rungsi Toulgoët, 1960 Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, male. Second report for Albania. Known in Albania from another habitat and locality near Butrint from June and October (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019).

Setina roscida ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: Slivnitsa, above Aldomirovsko Blato, 11.V.2024, 1 male.

Herminiinae

Orectis proboscidata (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]) Albania: Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 2 males and 2 females; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 29.VI.2024; Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 07.VIII.2024.

Macrochilo cribrumalis (Hübner, 1793) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 181). A new genus and new species for Albania.

Fig. 182. *Herminia tarsipennalis* ♀. AL, Dardhas 23.IX.2024.

Fig. 184. *Phytometra conicephala* ♀. NMK, Dračev Dol 11.VI.2024.

Fig. 183. *Herminia tarsicrinalis* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Herminia tarsipennalis Treitschke, 1835 Albania: Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 1 female (Fig. 182). A new genus and new species for Albania.

Herminia tarsicrinalis (Knoch, 1782) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 183). New species for Albania.

Herminia grisealis ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male.

Hypeninae

Zekelita antiqualis (Hübner, 1809) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024.

Hypena obesalis Treitschke, 1829 Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 1 female.

Hypena lividalis (Hübner, 1796) Montenegro: Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 13.XI.2023, 1 male;

Albania: Këlcyrës Gorge on Aoos River, 10.XI.2023, 1 male. A new species for Montenegro.

Rivulinae

Zebeeba falsalis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1839) Albania: Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 male.

Hypenodinae

Schranksia taenialis (Hübner, 1809) Bulgaria: Lyulin Mts, above Dragichevo, 18.VII.2022, 1 male, genitalia checked; E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked, in microvial in glycerol; Strandzha Mts, Papiya, 11.VII.2024, 1 female.

Boletobiinae

Phytometra conicephala (Staudinger, 1870) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 2 males and 1 female (Fig. 184); Bulgaria: Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna-Vlahi, 25.V.2024, 1 male.

Calymma communimacula ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024.

Eublemma ostrina (Hübner, [1808]) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male.

Eublemma rosea (Hübner, 1790) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 6 males and 2 females; Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 185). Second report for

Fig. 185. *Eublemma rosea* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Fig. 187. *Metachrostis velocior* ♂. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

Fig. 186. *Eublemma pudorina* ♂. NMK, Dračev Dol 11.VI.2024.

Fig. 188. *Metachrostis velocior* ♀. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

Albania, known previously from Zvezdë (Beshkov, 2018); North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 2 males and 1 female.

Eublemma pudorina (Staudinger, 1889) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 186). Second report for North Macedonia, known previously from the Vardar River Valley, above Demir Kapija Town on the road to Besvica Village (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020a).

Eublemma lacernaria (Hübner, [1813]) Albania: Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 1 male.

Metachrostis velox (Hübner, [1813]) Bulgaria: S. Pirin-Alibotush Mts, Gradishte between Nova Lovcha and Paril villages, 750 m, N41°26'00", E023°41'52", 23.VI.2014, rocky slopes with *Juniperus*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Quercus*, etc. S. Beshkov & S. Abadjiev leg., 1 male; Strandzha Mts, Papiya, 11.VII.2024.

Metachrostis velocior (Staudinger, 1892) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 15 males (Fig. 187) and 9 females (Fig. 188). Second report for Albania, known previously only from a single specimen from

the Ionian Sea coast, the shore near Dhërmi Village (Beshkov, 2017).

Metachrostis dardouini (Boisduval, 1840) Albania: Valamara Mts-Devoli Gorge, above Bratile Village, Gramsh Region, 999 m, N40.7723, E020.3351, 07.VI.2022, open stony area near road in *Quercus-Carpinus* forest; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 3 males and 2 females; Ibid, 18.VI.2024; Bulgaria: Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village, 14.VI.2023, 1 male.

Honeyana ragusana (Freyer, 1844) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 6 males and 1 female.

Toxocampinae

Lygephila pastinum (Treitschke, 1826) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 4 females; Serbia: Četnica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 4 males and 6 females.

Lygephila viciae (Hübner, 1822) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 female.

Fig. 189. *Catocala separata* ♀. AL, Gjorm 03.VII.2024.

Fig. 190. *Catocala dilecta* ♂. AL, Llogara 21.VI.2023 ups.

Fig. 191. *Catocala dilecta* ♂. AL, Llogara 21.VI.2023 unds.

Autophila ligaminosa (Eversmann, 1851) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male.

Erebinae

Zethes insularis Rambur, 1833 Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male.

Catocala separata Freyer, 1847 Albania: Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 female (Fig. 189); Bulgaria: Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 female.

Catocala diversa (Geyer, [1828]) Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 17.VIII.2024, 1 male.

Catocala fraxini (Linnaeus, 1758) Bulgaria: W. Stara Planina Mts, Venetsa above Belogradchik Town, 871 m, N43.62941, E022.70644, 24.IX.2022, limestone rocks with *Carpinus*, *Acer*, *Corylus collurna* forest, at light traps; W. Stara Planina Mts, Chiprovski Waterfall above Chiprovtsi Town, 935 m, N43.36301, E022.81871, 14.IX.2021, *Fagus* forest; W. Rhodopi Mts, Yadenitza River Valley above Golyamo Belovo, 1167 m, N42°06'15", E023°54'11", 06.IX.2012, *Quercus-Fagus* forest in deep river valley, S. Beshkov, M. Beshkova leg., 11 specimens; W. Rhodopi Mts, above Trigrad Gorge, 02.IX.2022, 1 male; W. Rhodopi Mts, Trigradski Skali Chalet below Trigrad Village, 1214 m, N41.6069, E024.3839, 20.VIII.2019, rocky river valley in limestone area, S. Beshkov & I. Stoychev leg. at 160W MVL.

Catocala coniuncta (Esper, 1787) Serbia: Vidlič, below Crni Vrh, 10.VIII.2024, 1 male. Second locality for Serbia, previously known only from above Trnava near Preševo in the second half of September (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2016).

Catocala dilecta (Hübner, [1808]) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male (Figs 190–191); Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 female. In Albania, *C. dilecta* is known from Muzina – Dhrovjan (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018) and from Tomori, 2379 m (Beshkov, Plant & Nahirnić, 2020). Third locality for Albania; Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 05.X.2022, S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova leg., 1 female.

Catocala lupina (Herrich-Schaffer, [1851]) Albania: Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 1 male (Fig. 192). New species for Albania.

Grammodes bifasciata (Petagna, 1876) Bulgaria: N Black Sea Coast, between Cape Kaliakra and Bulgarevo, 04.VIII.2022, 1 male.

Euteliidae

Eutelia adoratrix (Staudinger, 1892) Albania: Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 male.

Fig. 192. *Catocala lupina* ♂. AL, Dardhas 23.IX.2024.

Fig. 195. *Cornutiplusia circumflexa* ♂. AL, Kudhes 25.V.2023.

Fig. 193. *Euchalcia variabilis variabilis* ♂. SRB, Straža 9.VI.2024.

Fig. 194. *Euchalcia chlorocharis* ♂. AL, Tomori i Madh 15.VI.2024.

Noctuidae

Plusiinae

Thysanoplusia daubei (Boisduval, 1840) Albania: Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 female.

Euchalcia variabilis variabilis (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783) Serbia: Straža, 09.VI.2024, 3 males (Fig. 193).

Euchalcia variabilis fuscolivacea Varga & Ronkay, 1984 Bulgaria: Rila, above Karagyol reservoir below Kalin Peak, 25.VII.2023, 1 female. This is the highest locality of this taxon on the Balkan Peninsula. The population of high elevation in Rila, from where *Euchalcia variabilis fuscolivacea* is described, differs in appearance and is isolated from the population from the other parts of the Balkan Peninsula, especially in the central part of the Balkan Peninsula, which has a different habitat and flight period and is characterised by pinkish colouration.

Euchalcia modestoides Poole, 1989 Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024, 1 female.

Euchalcia chlorocharis (Dufay, 1961) Albania: Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 7 males (Fig. 194); Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male. *Euchalcia chlorocharis* is a Balkan endemic species, known only from North Macedonia, Greece and Albania.

Euchalcia consona (Fabricius, 1787) Bulgaria: Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 1 male.

Panchrysis deaurata (Esper, 1787) = *aurea* (Hübner, [1803]) Bulgaria: Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male.

Autographa bractea ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 male.

Cornutiplusia circumflexa (Linnaeus, 1767) Albania: Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 1 male (Fig. 195). Third locality for Albania. Previously reported from Fusha-Kuqe (Beshkov & Misja, 1995) and from Gorica [Korca Region] (Beshkov et al., 1996).

Plusia festucae (Linnaeus, 1758) Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 17.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 male.

Fig. 196. *Pseudozarba bipartita* ♀. NMK, Dračev Dol 11.VI.2024.

Fig. 198. *Acontia titania* ♂. Al, Gjorm 03.VII.2024.

Fig. 197. *Janthinea friwaldszkii* ♀. BG, Mramor 03.VI.2024.

Eustrotiinae

Phyllophila obliterata (Rambur, 1833) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male.

Pseudozarba bipartita (Herrich-Schaffer, [1850]) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 female; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male and 2 females (Fig. 196).

Acontiinae

Janthinea friwaldszkii (Duponchel, 1835) Bulgaria: Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, at a daytime on *Anchusa officinalis*, 1 female (Fig. 197).

Acontia titania (Esper, 1798) = *urania* Frivaldsky, 1835 Albania: Lumi i Shushices, above Gjorm, 03.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 198); North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024; Bulgaria: Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 2 males, Sakar, Shtit,

01.VI.2024, 3 males; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 2 males.

Ponometia candefacta (Hübner, [1831]) Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 female; Veliki Čukar, 29.VI.2024, 1 male; Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 07.VIII.2024, 1 male; Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 1 female; Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 08.VII.2024, 2 males; Strandzha, Popovi Skali, 09.VII.2024, 2 males; Strandzha “Pirena” above Kosti, 10.VII.2024, 1 female; Strandzha Mts, Papiya, 11.VII.2024. *Ponometia candefacta* has not been reported from Southern Bulgaria before.

Pantheinae

Panthea coenobita (Esper, [1785]) Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 2 males; Bulgaria: Rila, near Makedonia Chalet, 23.VII.2023, 1 male.

Acronictinae

Moma alpium (Osbeck, 1778) Serbia: Straža, 09.VI.2024; Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 female; Sakar Mt, below Vishegrad, near Kostur, 04.VI.2024.

Simyra dentinosa Freyer, [1838] Albania: Mali i Thatë (= Galičica Mts) above Bregas (= Korita) Village, N40.809444, E20.833890, 1454 m, 15.VI.2024, dry stony slopes with scarce vegetation, at daytime, caterpillar last instar on *Euphorbia* sp. (Fig. 199). Second locality for Albania, previously known only from Fusha e Korabit [Griba Mt, Maja e

Fig. 199. *Simyra dentinosa*, caterpillar last instar. AL, above Bregas 15.VI.2024.

Tartarit], also from larvae found on *Euphorbia* more than 90 years ago (Rebel & Zerny, 1931; Heinicke, 1965).

Acronicta alni (Linnaeus, 1767) Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 3 males and 1 female (Fig. 200). New species for Greece.

Acronicta strigosa ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: Sofia Region, Kostinbrod distr. above Beledie Han Village, 800 m, N42.89231, E023.15850, 08.VIII.2021, limestone slopes with *Artemisia alba* near *Quercus-Carpinus* forest, 1 male at 8W light trap; Strandzha, Popovi Skali, 09.VII.2024, 1 male.

Acronicta orientalis (Mann, 1862) Albania: Progonat, 22.VI.2023, 2 females (Fig. 201); Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 female; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 4 males.

Craniophora pontica (Staudinger, 1879) Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 30.VI.2021, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, 1 male; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 1 female.

Metoponinae

Apaustis rupicola ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo, 491 m, 03.VI.2023.

Aegle semicana (Esper, 1798) = *vespertalis* (Hübner, [1811-1813]) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 1 female.

Aegle kaekeritziana (Hübner, [1799]) Bulgaria: NW above Glushnik Village, 02.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 202).

Fig. 200. *Acronicta alni* ♀. GR, Vigla 12.VI.2024.

Fig. 201. *Acronicta orientalis* ♀. AL, Progonat 22.VI.2023.

Fig. 202. *Aegle kaekeritziana* ♂. BG, Glushnik 2.VI.2023.

Haemerosia renalis (Hübner, [1813]) Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 2 males.

Haemerosia vassilininei A. Bang-Haas, 1912 Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 08.VII.2024.

Cuculliinae

Calocucullia celsiae (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850) Serbia: Bela Palanka, above Moklište, 07.IV.2024, 1 female;

Fig. 203. *Cucullia lactucae* ♂. BG, Makedonia Chalet 23.VII.2023.

Fig. 205. *Cucullia xeranthemi* ♂. AL, Trebunit 25.VIII.2023.

Fig. 204. *Cucullia lucifuga* ♂. SRB, Karaula 30.V.2024.

Fig. 206. *Cucullia xeranthemi* ♀. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 1 male.

Cucullia formosa Rogenhofer, 1860 Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 2 males.

Cucullia lactucae ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked; Bulgaria: W Stara Planina Mts, above Chuprene Village, Popovitsa below Gorski Ray Chalet, 1074 m, N43.4621, E022.6156, 24.VI.2022, forest in a river valley and slopes with *Pteridium aquilinum*, 1 female; Rila, near Makedonia Chalet, 23.VII.2023, 1 male (Fig. 203); Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 male and 1 female, male genitalia checked.

Cucullia lucifuga ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 204), genitalia checked.

Cucullia santonici (Hübner, [1813]) Albania: Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 2 males; Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 04.VII.2012, 1 male; Ibid, 29.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski

Fig. 207. *Cucullia dracunculi* ♂. NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024.

Krust, 12.VII.2023, 1 female; Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 male.

Cucullia xeranthemi Boisduval, 1840 Albania: Puke, Trebunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 male (Fig. 205) and 1 female; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male and 2 females (Fig. 206).

Cucullia dracunculi (Hübner, [1813]) North Macedonia: Prilep, Pletvar Pass, 05.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 207). Reported as a new species for North

Fig. 208. *Shargacucullia gozmanyi* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

Fig. 210. *Sympistis michaelorum srnkai* ♂. SRB, Divna Gorica 1186 m 09.VIII.2024.

Fig. 209. *Behounekia freyeri* ♂. BG, Sladun 02.V.2024.

Macedonia from almost the same place, but collected there in August (Beshkov & Nahirmić, 2019).

Shargacucullia thapsiphaga (Treitschke, 1826) Albania: Prespa Lake, near Glloboçeni Village, 18.V.2023, 1 male.

Shargacucullia blattariae (Esper, 1790) Albania: Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023, 1 male; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 1 female.

Shargacucullia gozmanyi G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay, 1994 Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male (Fig. 208). New species for Serbia.

Oncocnemidiinae

Calophasia platyptera (Esper, 17887) Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 1 male; Qafa e Pashkasheshit above Iba, 21.V.2023, 1 male with polinia on the head; Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 1 male.

Calophasia barthae Wagner, 1929 Bulgaria: Sakar, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male.

Behounekia freyeri (Frivaldszky, 1935) Bulgaria: Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 1 male (Fig. 209).

Omphalophana anatolica (Lederer, 1857) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 1 male; Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 1 female; Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male and 1 female; Sakar, Oreshnik, 06.V.2024, 2 males; Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 1 female.

Sympistis michaelorum srnkai (Beshkov, 2021) Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 2 males (Fig. 210) in light trap. Access to the collecting locality is possible only on foot, about a half-hour walk. A new genus and new species for Serbia. *Sympistis michaelorum srnkai* was previously known only from Bulgaria in the Dragoman Natura 2000 Protected area between Ponor Village above Kostinbrod Town and Petrovski Krust Summit in Chepan Hill above Dragoman Town (Beshkov, 2021). Because the type locality in Bulgaria is close to Serbia, we searched for *Sympistis michaelorum srnkai* at light several times in similar habitats [*Satureja montana*] on Rtanj Mt above Mužinac Village, on Šljivovički Vis Mt above Bela Palanka, above Moklište Village near Bela Palanka, below Crni Vrh on Vidlič Mt above Pirot, above Gulenovci Village in Vidlič Mt and between Bačevo and Dimitrovgrad Town. *Sympistis michaelorum srnkai* is an endemic subspecies for Bulgaria and Serbia. *Sympistis michaelorum michaelorum* (Beshkov, 1997) is a local endemic for the Silvercoast (N Black Sea Coast of Bulgaria) (Beshkov, 2021).

Epimecia ustula (Freyer, 1835) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 1 male; Ibid, 21.VI.2023, 1 male; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 1 male;

Fig. 211. *Praestilbia armeniaca* ♂. AL, Trebunit 25.VIII.2023.

Fig. 213. *Teinoptera lunaki* ♂. NMK, Dračev Dol 11.VI.2024.

Fig. 212. *Praestilbia armeniaca* ♀. AL, Trebunit 25.VIII.2023.

Fig. 214. *Teinoptera lunaki* ♂. BG, Kresna-Vlahi 25.V.2024.

Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 3 males; Vidlič, below Crni Vrh, 10.VIII.2024; Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 1 female; Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 1 male; Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 2 males.

Praestilbia armeniaca Staudinger, 1892 Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 2 males (Fig. 211) and 1 female (Fig. 212); Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 3 males; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 21.IX.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, NW of Shtit, 12.X.2024, 1 male; Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 1 male.

Teinoptera lunaki (Boursin, 1840) Albania: Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebren, 11.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 213); Bulgaria: Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlahi, 25.V.2024, 3 males (Fig. 214); Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 female.

Fig. 215. *Cleonymia opposita* ♀. BG, Oreshnik 06.V.2024.

Cleonymia opposita (Lederer, 1870) Albania: Prespa Lake, near Gllloboçeni Village, 18.V.2022. 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, Oreshnik, 06.V.2024, 4 males and 1 female (Fig. 215).

Amephana dalmatica (Rebel, 1919) Albania: Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 2 males; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 28.V.2023, 7 males; Ibid, 23.VI.2023, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024.

Fig. 216. *Asteroscopus sphinx* ♂. MNE, Povija 13.XI.2023.

Fig. 217. *Helivictoria victorina* ♂. AL, Ptespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Fig. 218. *Helivictoria victorina* ♂. AL, Ptespa e vogel, Tren 13.VI.2024, on *Salvia sclarea*.

Amphipyridae

Amphipyra effusa (Boisduval, 1828) Albania: Liqeni Prespa e vogel, near Tren Village, 865 m, N40.6722, E020.9874, 13.VI.2024, small cave near marsh area

with *Phragmites*, *Nymphaea* and limestone slopes around with *Buxus* and *Carpinus*, single specimen observed aestivating in the cave.

Amphipyra perflua (Fabricius, 1787) Montenegro: Rožaje, Vrelo Ibra, 23.VIII.2023, 1 male.

Amphipyra stix Herrich-Schäffer, 1850 Serbia: Vidlič, below Crni Vrh, 10.VIII.2024, 1 female; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024.

Amphipyra tetra (Fabricius, 1787) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 male; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male; Suva Planina above Bela Palanka, 06.IX.2024, 1 male; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male; Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 1 female; Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 female.

Amphipyra micans Lederer, 1857 Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 female; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male.

Brachionycha nubeculosa (Esper, 1785) Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 3 males and 2 females.

Asteroscopus sphinx (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Tepelene Region, Drino River, 27.XI.2024, 2 males; Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 26.XI.2024, 1 male in negative temperature in the morning. Montenegro: Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 13.XI.2023, 1 small male (Fig. 216), genitalia checked.

Heliothinae

Helivictoria victorina (Sodiffsky, 1849) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 19 males and 3 females on lamps and light traps (Fig. 217) and at daytime on flowers of *Salvia sclarea* (Fig. 218). Second report for Albania, previously known from Kolonjë near Tepelene (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019).

Philareta treitschkii (Frigivaldszky, 1835) Bulgaria: Tsegrilovtsi Village near Trun, 18.VII.1972, Al. Petrov leg., in coll. NMNHS; Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, 4 males and 3 females (Fig. 219). This species has not been found in Bulgaria for more than 30 years, even in the localities where it was known before – Kresna Gorge and the Volcanic Hill of Kozhuh near Petrich Town.

Fig. 219. *Philareta treitschkii* ♀. BG, Mramor 03.VI.2025.

Fig. 221. *Pyrrhia purpura* ♀. AL, Kudhes 25.V.2023.

Fig. 220. *Pyrrhia purpura* ♂. AL, Kudhes 25.V.2023.

Fig. 222. *Pyrrhia purpura* ♂. BG, Topolovgrad 07.V.2024.

Periphanes delphinii (Linnaeus, 1758) Bulgaria: Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Pyrrhia purpura (Hübner, [1817]) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 3 females; Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 4 males (Fig. 220) and 7 females (Fig. 221); Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male. New species for Albania. North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 female. Second record for North Macedonia, previously reported from Dedeli near Valandovo and Nikolić on Dojran Lake, collected there more than 100 years ago (Hacker, 1989); Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad, 07.V.2024, 1 male (Fig. 222); Sakar, Shtit, 17.V.2024, 1 female; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 female; Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 2 males.

Heliothis nubigera Herrich-Schäffer, [1851] Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 1 female.

Heliothis incarnata Freyer, [1838] Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 2 males and 1 female; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024.

Condicinae

Condica viscosa (Freyer, [1831]) Albania: Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 1 male. In Albania known from Stan Karbunarë (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019) and wrongly reported and illustrated from Ardenica in Beshkov & Nahirić, (2019a) as *Phyllophila obliterata* (Rambur, 1833) (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019). Second report for Albania.

Eucarta amethystina (Hübner, [1803]) Serbia: Kruševac Region, Čelijsko jezero near Čelije Village, 295 m, N43.4206, E021.1798, 06.VIII.2024, dark forest near water reservoir, 1 male.

Bryophilinae

Cryphia algae (Fabricius, 1775) Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024, male genitalia checked.

Cryphia ochsi (Boursin, 1840) Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024, male genitalia checked; Alibotush, above Goleshovo, 05.IX.2013, 1 male.

Fig. 223. *Bryophila seladona burgeffi* ♀. BG, Dzenda, 22.IX.2023.

Fig. 224. *Bryophila raptricula* ♂. AL, Plani i Bardhe 30.IX.2018.

Fig. 225. *Bryophila raptricula* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar 29.VI.2024 GP2.10.III.2025.

Bryophila seladona burgeffi (Draudt, 1931) Bulgaria: E Rhodopi, Zhenda, The rock mushroom, 22.IX.2023, 1 male and 3 females (Fig. 223).

Bryophila rectilinea (Warren, 1909) Albania: Prespa Lake, near Pustec Village, 849 m, N40.7706, E020.9089, 19.VIII.2017, *Typha*, *Phragmites*, *Mentha*, lake shore, 1 female.

Fig. 226. *Bryophila raptricula* male genitalia with everted vesica. SRB, Rtanj 21.VIII.2023, GP 3./11.III.2025.

Bryophila tephrocharis (Boursin, 1954) Albania: Ersekë County, above Borovë, 21.VII.2022, 2 males; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 01.VII.2019, S. Beshkov, A. Nahirnić, P. Jakšić, C. Plant, A. King leg., 1 male and 1 female.

Bryophila raptricula ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Mt Thanës, near Bulqizë Town, above Plani i Bardhë Village, 767 m, N41.4762, E020.1554, 30.IX.2018, stony slopes with *Artemisia*, *Quercus*, *Pinus nigra*, 2 males (Fig. 224), genitalia checked, one with everted vesica in microvial in glycerol, dissected March 2025; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 29.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 225), gen. prep. 2./10.III.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 07.VIII.2024, 1 male, gen. prep. 3./11.III.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal (Fig. 226); Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 2 males, gen. preps 1./11.III.2025 and 2./11.III.2025 (Fig. 227), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 2 males, gen. preps 1./12.III.2025 (Figs 228–230) and 1./13.III.2025 (Figs 231–232), S. Beshkov, male genitalia

Fig. 227. *Bryophila raptricula* male genitalia with everted vesica. SRB, Bačevo 11.VIII.2024, GP 2./11.III.2025.

Fig. 228. *Bryophila raptricula* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Krivonoska mogila 02.IX.2023, GP 1./12.III.2025, covered.

Fig. 229. *Bryophila raptricula* everted vesica BG, Krivonoska mogila 02.IX.2023, GP 1./12.III.2025, not covered.

Fig. 230. *Bryophila raptricula* everted vesica. BG, Krivonoska mogila 02.IX.2023, GP 1./12.III.2025, not covered.

Fig. 231. *Bryophila raptricula* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Krivonoska mogila 02.IX.2023, GP 1./13.III.2025.

Fig. 232. *Bryophila raptricula* everted vesica. BG, Krivonoska mogila 02.IX.2023, GP 1./13.III.2025.

Fig. 233. *Bryophila raptricula* ♀. BG, Kaliakra-Bulgarevo 04.VIII.2022, GP 1./14.III.2025.

Fig. 234. *Bryophila raptricula* female genitalia. BG, Kaliakra-Bulgarevo 04.VIII.2022, GP 1./14.III.2025.

with everted vesica on glass in euparal; N Black Sea Coast, between Cape Kaliakra and Bulgarevo, 04.VIII.2022, 1 female (Fig. 233), gen. prep. 1./14.III.2025 (Figs 234–236), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal; N Black Sea Coast, Cape Kaliakra, disused well, 05.VIII.2022, 1 male, genitalia with everted vesica in microvial in glycerol, vesica damaged.

Figs 235–236. [235 left] *Bryophila raptricula* female genitalia. BG, Kaliakra-Bulgarevo 04.VIII.2022, GP 1./14.III.2025; [236 right] *Bryophila raptricula* female genitalia. BG, Kaliakra-Bulgarevo 04.VIII.2022, GP 1./14.III.2025.

Bryophila felina (Eversmann, 1852) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 237), gen. prep. 1./10.III.2025 (Fig. 238), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Tirana, Dajt Mt, Shkalla Village, 893 m, N41.3303, E019.9653, 23.VII.2017, *Castanea sativa*, *Spartium junceum*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Artemisia alba*, 1 female (Fig. 239), gen. prep. 3./14.III.2025 (Fig. 240), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal; Mali i Thatë (Galičica Mts) above Bregas (= Korita) Village, 1485 m, N40.8095, E020.8347. 20.VIII.2017, overgrazed limestone slopes with *Astragalus*, *Crataegus*, etc., 1 male, gen. prep. 2./14.III.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Serbia: Bujanovac Region, Starac Mt, Turski Grob near Pčinja River Valley, 799 m, N42.32442, E021.8839, 26.VIII.2015, silicate dry meadows with *Juniperus* near *Quercus-Carpinus* forest, 3 males and 1 female; Niš Region, Suva Planina, above Bojanine Vode, 1000 m, N43.2156,

Fig. 237. *Bryophila felina* ♂. AL, Llogara 21.VI.2023, GP 1./10.III.2025.

Fig. 239. *Bryophila felina* ♀. AL, Shkalla 27.VIII.2018, GP 3./14.III.2025.

Fig. 238. *Bryophila felina* male genitalia with everted vesica. AL, Llogara, 21.VI.2023, GP 1./10.III.2025.

Fig. 240. *Bryophila felina* female genitalia. AL, Shkalla 27.VIII.2018, GP 3./14.III.2025.

E022.1242, 02.VII.2014, meadow near *Fagus* forest, 2 males (Fig. 241), gen. prep. 1./28.III.2025 (Figs 242–243), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; North Macedonia: Prilep, Pletvar Pass, 05.VII.2024, 1 male, gen. prep. 3./13.III.2025 (Figs 244–246), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male, gen. prep. 4./11.III.2025 (Figs 247–248), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal and 1 female, gen. prep. 4./13.III.2025 (Fig. 249), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal; Bulgaria: Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 male, gen. prep. 4./10.III.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with

everted vesica on glass in euparal; Suhata Reka above Kapitan Dimitrovo, 11.VIII.2022, 2 males, gen. preps 3./10.III.2025 (Fig. 250) and 5./11.III.2025 (Figs 251–252), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; N Black Sea Coast, Silvercoast, below Topola village between Balchik

Fig. 241. *Bryophila felina* ♂. SRB, Bojanine Vode 02.VII.2014 GP 1./28.III.2025.

Fig. 244. *Bryophila felina* male genitalia with everted vesica. NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024, GP 3./13.III.2025.

Fig. 242. *Bryophila felina* male genitalia with everted vesica. SRB, Bojanine Vode 02.VII.2014 GP 1./28.III.2025.

Fig. 245. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024, GP 3./13.III.2025.

Fig. 243. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. SRB, Bojanine Vode 02.VII.2014, GP 1./28.III.2025.

Fig. 246. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024, GP 3./13.III.2025.

Fig. 247. *Bryophila felina* male genitalia with everted vesica. NMK, Rebre 11.VI.2024, GP 4./11.III.2025.

Fig. 248. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. NMK, Rebre 11.VI.2024, GP 4./11.III.2025.

and Kavarna towns, 34 m, N43.40956, E028.2606, 02.VIII.2022, sandy rocks with *Artemisia*, *Jasminum*, *Paliurus*, etc. 1 male, gen. prep. 2./13.III.2025 (Figs 253–255), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal.

All single illustrated vesicas for both *B. raptricula* and *B. felina* were photographed in alcohol before mounting in Euparal and covered with glass. New species for Serbia, North Macedonia and Albania, and with first clear localities for Bulgaria, from where it is only mentioned to be present (Fibiger et al., 2010). Both species *B. felina* and *B. raptricula* can be certainly separated after examination of the female genitalia and the everted vesica of the male genitalia.

Fig. 249. *Bryophila felina* female genitalia. NMK, Rebre 11.VI.2024, GP 4./13.III.2025.

Fig. 250. *Bryophila felina* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Kapitan Dimitrovo, 11.VIII.2022, GP 3./10.III.2025.

Fig. 251. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. BG, Kapitan Dimitrovo 11.VIII.2022, GP 5.11.III.2025.

Fig. 254. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. BG, below Topola 02.VIII.2022, GP 2./13.III.2025.

Fig. 252. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. BG, Kapitan Dimitrovo, 11.VIII.2022, GP 5.11.III.2025.

Fig. 255. *Bryophila felina* everted vesica. BG, below Topola, 02.VIII.2022, GP 2./13.III.2025.

Fig. 253. *Bryophila felina* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, below Topola, 02.VIII.2022, GP 2./13.III.2025.

In *B. felina* everted vesica is large and lies in a plane, whereas in *B. raptricula* in the basal part there is a diverticulum, arising laterally. Externally, *B. felina* has darker hindwings and also more rusty and coloured forewings. The distribution pattern of *B. felina* and *B. raptricula* on the Balkan Peninsula is not yet sufficiently clarified.

Noctuinae

Spodoptera littoralis (Boisduval, 1833) Albania: Ksamil, 28.XI.2024, 2 males; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 female.

Caradrina terrea Freyer, [1839] Serbia: Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 21.VIII.2023, 2 males; Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 3 males and 1 female; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 3 males and 2 females; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near

Fig. 256. *Caradrina pertinax argentea* ♂. BG, Bukvite 01.VIII.2022.

Fig. 258. *Caradrina wullschlegeli* ♂. AL, Maja e Manjolave 20.VI.2023.

Fig. 257. *Caradrina suscianja* ♂. AL, Tomori 16.VI.2024.

Fig. 259. *Chilodes maritima* ♂. BG, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024.

Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male; Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 17.VIII.2024, 2 males; above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024.

Caradrina pertinax argentea (Caradja, 1930) Bulgaria: Silvercoast, “Bukvite” above Balchik Town, 181 m, N43.4065, E028.1769, 01.VIII.2022, sandy rocks with *Atrémisia*, etc., 10 males (Fig. 256) and 1 female; N Black Sea Coast, Cape Kaliakra, disused well, 05.VIII.2022, 1 female. Recently, four taxa from the Silvercoast of Bulgaria (Beshkov, 1997; Zlatkov, Beshkov & Huemer, 2021) and one from the Black Sea Coast of Romania (L. Ronkay, in press) with silver or whitish colouration were described, so we recognise the coastal and isolated population of *Caradrina pertinax argentea* as a subspecies, which can be easily separated in appearance from the nominotypical species.

Caradrina gilva (Donzel, 18327) Montenegro: Maglić Mt, above Pivsko jezero, Šturbina above Mratinje Village, 1175 m, N43.2686, E018.82, 08.VIII.2015, limestone area with *Fagus*, *Quercus*,

Fraxinus, *Acer*, *Juniperus communis*, etc., 1 male at light trap; Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 2 males; Progonat, 22.VI.2023, 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 male; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024; Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 2 females. This is the lowest and northernmost locality of *C. gilva* in Bulgaria. This locality is close to the border to Serbia, which suggests that *C. gilva* may occur in eastern Serbia as well.

Caradrina suscianja (von Mentzer, 1981) Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 7 males (Fig. 257); Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 3 males; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 8 males; Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Caradrina wullschlegeli Püngeler, 1903 Albania: Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 258) and 3 females; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male; Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 05.VI.2022, 1 male;

Fig. 260. *Hydrillula pallustris* ♂. AL, Mali me Gropa 1466 m, 19.VI.2023.

Fig. 261. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* ♂. BG, Tsar Petrovo 02.V.2010, GP 1./20.II.2025.

Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 2 males.

Chilodes maritima (Tauscher, 1806) Bulgaria: Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 259).

Proxenus hospes (Freyer, 1831) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 03.VII.2021, 1 male; Straža, 09.VI.2024; Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 1 female. Second report for Serbia. For Serbia, it was published recently by Stojanović et al. (2024) from Zlotski kanjon near Bor and “Gornje Podunavlje” Nature Reserve. Bulgaria: Sakar, above Sladun Village, 18.V.2024, 1 female; N Black Sea Coast, Silvercoast, “Bukvite” above Balchik Town, 181 m, N43.4065, E028.1769, 01.VIII.2022, sandy rocks with *Artemisia*, etc., 1 male.

Hydrillula pallustris (Hübner, 1808) Albania: Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 260). New species for Albania; Bulgaria: W Stara Planina Mts, Zarezan Cheshma above Chuprene on Chuprenska Reka river, 674 m, N43.4874,

Fig. 262. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Tsar Petrovo 02.V.2010, GP 1./20.II.2025.

Fig. 263. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Musselievo 01.V.2012, GP 1./28.II.2025.

E022.6154, 24.VI.2021, forest and meadows in river valley, 1 female.

Gracilathetis kovacssandori Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024 Bulgaria: Vidin Region, Tsar Petrovo Village between Vidin and Kula, the old road to Vidin, 223 m, N43.8689, E022.6508, 02.V.2010,

Fig. 264. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* ♂. BG, Popovi Skali 09.VII.2024, GP 1./04.II.2025.

Fig. 265. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* male genitalia. BG, Popovi Skali 09.VII.2024, GP 1./04.II.2025.

Fig. 266. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* everted vesica, not covered. BG, Popovi Skali 09.VII.2024, GP 1./04.II.2025.

Fig. 267. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* everted vesica, in Euparal. BG, Popovi Skali 09.VII.2024, GP 1./04.II.2025.

Fig. 268. *Gracilathetis kovacssandori* female genitalia BG, Balchik-Kavarna, 22–27.VII.1992, GP 2./03.X.1997.

meadows and light forest with *Acer tataricum*, *Acer campestre*, *Quercus*, *Ulmus*, *Crataegus*, S. Beshkov & T. Yanakiev leg., 1 male (Fig. 261), gen. prep. 1./20.II.2025 (Fig. 262), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Danube Plain, Nikopolsko Plato plateau, the Quarry above Muselievo Village on the road to Vubel, 110 m, N43.6456, E024.8661, 01.V.2012, limestone area with *Ailanthus* and steppes with *Artemisia alba*, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg., 21 males and 12 females, gen. prep. 1./28.II.2025 (Fig. 263), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Danube Plain, Nikopolsko Plato plateau, near Nikopol Town, 135 m, N43.6892, E024.8928, 30.IV.2012, *Quercus*, *Acer tataricum*, meadows, S. Beshkov & M. Beshkova leg., 2 males

and 2 females; Strandzha, Popovi Skali, 09.VII.2024, 2 males (Fig. 264), gen. prep. 1./04. II.2025, S. Beshkov, male genitalia (Fig. 265) with everted vesica (Figs 266–267) on glass in euparal; N Black Sea Coast, Cape Kaliakra, disused well, 05.VIII.2022, 1 male; N Black Sea Coast, Durankulak Lake, near the Sea Coast near Krapets Camping, 3 m, N43.6613, E028.5661, 08.VIII.2022, sandy beach, trees, *Phragmites*, *Artemisia*, etc., 1 male, genitalia with everted vesica in microvial in glycerol. *Athetis lepigone* is mentioned in Beshkov (2013) as confirmed for Bulgaria, but without any further data. The source is a single female specimen collected on the Silver Coast between Balchik and Kavarna, 22–27.VII.1992, gen. prep. 2./03.X.1997 (Fig. 268). In Bulgaria, *Gracuilathetis lepigone* (Moschler, 1860) is supposedly recorded (only) from the N Black Sea Coast: Cape Shabla (Beshkov, 1992; Beshkov, 2000), Kranevo village, Dourankoulak Lake, Touzlata between Balchik and Kavarna towns (Beshkov, 2000), but all these reports must concern *Gracuilathetis kovacssandori*. All specimens examined from Bulgaria (Vidin area, Danube Plain, Black Sea Coast, and Strandzha) are indeed *Gracuilathetis kovacssandori*, which is confirmed by examination of the genitalia, including everted vesicae. A new species for the Balkan Peninsula and Bulgaria, until now known only from the type series from the Carpathian Basin (Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024).

Mormo maura (Linnaeus, 1758) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 female at light (Fig. 269); Tirana Region, Vora Village, 260 m, 27.VI.1995, two specimens aestivating in a gallery of a bunker; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male.

Olivenebula subsericata (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 male; Bulgaria: above Bosnek, (1197 m a.s.l.), 24.VIII.2024, 1 male. This seems to be the highest locality of this species in Bulgaria; Krichim, Izgoryaloto Gyune, 23.IX.2023, 1 female.

Actinotia radiosa (Esper, [1804]) Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 270) at light.

Auchmis detersa (Esper, [1791]) Bulgaria: Pirin Mts, Bansko Town, 983 m, N41°49'39"; E023°28'56", 24.VII.2019, at a lamp in the town. The nominotypical form is very rare in Bulgaria, known from old reports, some of them doubtful, only from

Fig. 269. *Mormo maura* ♀. AL, Llogara 21.VI.2023.

Fig. 270. *Actinotia radiosa* ♂. GR, Vigla 12.VI.2024.

Fig. 271. *Auchmis detersa argentea* ♂. BG, Pobitite Kamani 07.IX.2022.

Stara Planina Mts – Sliven, Gabrovo, Etropole, Teteven, summarised in Beshkov (2000) and from Zemen Gorge (Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov, 2000). Probably all reports from Black Sea Coast concern *Auchmis detersa argentea* (Caradja) (Beshkov, 2000), see below.

Auchmis detersa argentea (Caradja, 1932) Bulgaria: Northern Black Sea Coast, the main group of “Pobitite Kamani”, Varna Region, 106 m, N43.2234, E027.7068, 07.IX.2022, sandy area with

Fig. 272. *Photedes morrisii simonyisandori* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Balchik 27.VI.2003, GP 3./20. II.2025.

grass vegetation, S. Beshkov, R. Wasala & A. Nahirić-Beshkova leg., 3 males (Fig. 271) and 2 females. The taxonomic status is doubtful, but this population on the north Black Sea Coast differs in color from the nominotypical species and inhabits the coastal area at low altitude. It is on wing from the very end of May (30.V.2003) to the second half of September (10.IX.2014).

Gortyna moesiaca Herrich-Schäffer, 1849 Bulgaria: E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo, 566 m, 07.X.2023, 1 male.

Luperina dumerilii (Duponchel, 1826) Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male and 2 females; Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 07.IX.2024, 1 male.

Luperina rubella (Duponchel, [1837]) Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 4 males; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 20.IV.2024, 1 male.

Rhizedra lutosa (Hübner, [1803]) Bulgaria: Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 1 female.

Oria musculosa (Hübner, [1808]) Bulgaria: Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 1 female.

Photedes captiuncula (Treitschke, 1825) Serbia: above Veliki Čukar, 982 m, 03.VII.2021, 1 male at light; Bulgaria: Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 male at light.

Photedes minima (Haworth, 1809) Bulgaria: Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets, 21.VII.2024, 1 male; Lyulin Mts, above Dragichevo, 18.VII.2022, 1 male, genitalia checked.

Photedes morrisii simonyisandori Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024 In Bulgaria, reported as the nominotypical subspecies only from the Black Sea Coast – Nessebar (Soffner, 1962), the districts of Burgas and Balchik area (Beshkov, 2017a). Examination of the male genitalia, mainly the basal diverticula and the bulbed cornutus (Fig. 272), shows that the population of Bulgaria and Albania belongs to ssp. *simonyisandori* Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga. Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 females. Third locality for Albania. Known before previously from Boboshticë (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2018b) and Ersekë Region, above Borovë Village, 1096 m (Beshkov, Nahirić-Beshkova & Jakšić, 2024). A new taxon for the Balkan Peninsula, as it has to replace the nominotypical species.

Apamea syriaca (Osthelder, 1933) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 24.V.2023, 1 male; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 1 male; Prespa Lake, near Glloboçenii Village, 18.V.2022. 1 male; Ibid, 04.VI.2022, 4 males; Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 01.V.2024, 1 male, wingspan 49.5 mm.

Apamea sublustris (Esper, [1788]) Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 17.VII.2023, 2 females; Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 female.

Apamea platinea (Treitschke, 1825) Montenegro: Durmitor Mts, Veliki Štuoc, 06.VIII.2015, 1 male; Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 male; Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 1 male.

Apamea rubirena (Treitschke, 1825) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: W. Stara Planina Mts, above Berkovitsa Town, Kom Chalet, the old one, 1628 m, N43.1819, E023.0787, 16.VII.2021, meadows and clearings in coniferous forest, 1 male and 1 female.

Fig. 273. *Apamea sordens* ♂. AL, Maja Achishtes 28.V.2023.

Fig. 275. *Episema lederi* ♂. BG, Topolovgrad 13.X.2024.

Fig. 274. *Apamea aquila* ♀. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

Fig. 276. *Tiliacea cypreago christiani* ♂. MNE, Drume 12.XI.2023.

Apamea sordens (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 28.V.2023, 1 male (Fig. 273).

Apamea remissa (Hübner, [1809]) Serbia: Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 2 males.

Apamea aquila Donzel, 1837 Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 female (Fig. 274). New species for Albania.

Apamea epomidion (Haworth, 1809) Serbia: Ćetanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 female.

Episema tersa ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male.

Episema lederi Christoph, 1885 Bulgaria: Sakar, above Topolovgrad, 13.X.2024, 1 male (Fig. 275).

Cleoceris scoriacea (Esper, [1789]) Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male.

Ulochlaena hirta (Hübner, [1813]) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2023, 1 male.

Atethmia ambusta ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 1 female; Serbia: Suva Planina above Bela Palanka, 06.IX.2024, 1 female; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 07.IX.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male; Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 1 female.

Tiliacea cypreago christiani Fibiger, 1992 Montenegro: Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 276). A new species for Montenegro; Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 2 males; Prespa Lake, near Gilloboçeni Village, 05–06.XI.2023, 1 female.

Xanthia togata (Esper, 1788) Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 2 males.

Anchoscelis deleta (Staudinger, 1881) Bulgaria: Sakar, NW of Shtit, 12.X.2024, 3 males (Fig. 277).

Anchoscelis kindermannii (Fisher von Röslerstamm, 1838) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar

Fig. 277. *Anchoscelis deleta* ♂. BG, Shtit 12.X.2024.

Fig. 280. *Anchoscelis kindermannii* ♂. AL, Lin 25.XI.2024.

Fig. 278. *Anchoscelis kindermannii* ♂. B&H, Jasen 14.XI.2023.

Fig. 281. *Anchoscelis rupicapra kresnaensis* ♂. NMK, Rebre 3.XI.2023.

Fig. 279. *Anchoscelis kindermannii* ♀. MNE, Polija 13.XI.2023.

Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 2 males (Fig. 278) and 1 female; Montenegro: Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 13.XI.2023 (Fig. 279). A new species for Montenegro; Albania: Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 25.XI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 280) and 1 female; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2024, 1 male and 8 females.

Anchoscelis rupicapra kresnaensis Ronkay & Mészáros, 1982 North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2024, 5 males (Fig. 281) and 3 females. Second locality for North Macedonia, known previously only from Besvica above Demir Kapija Town (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2018a).

Anchoscelis osthelderi (Boursin, 1952) Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi, Zhenda, The rock mushroom, 22.IX.2023, 3 males (Figs 282–283) and 2 females.

Leptologia lota (Clerck, 1759) Albania: Pogradec Region, Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 693 m, N41.0510, E020.6431, 08.XI.2023, lake shore with *Platanus orientalis*, *Quercus trojana* bushes, etc. 2 males, in rain. Second locality for Albania, known previously only from Këlcyrë (= Klisura) Gorge (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2020a).

Leptologia macilenta (Hübner, [1809]) Albania: Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 25.XI.2024, 1 female.

Spudaea pontica (Klyuchko, 1968) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Struma River Valley-S Pirin Mts, above

Fig. 282. *Anchoscelis osthelderi* ♂. BG Dzenda 22.IX.2023.

Fig. 284. *Lithophane merckii* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

Fig. 283. *Anchoscelis osthelderi* ♂. BG Dzenda 22.IX.2023.

Fig. 285. *Ipimorpha subtusa* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren 13.VI.2024.

Kresna Town from the roar to Vlahi, 529 m, N41.73034, E023.2003. 07.I.2023, slopes with *Juniperus excelsa*, *Quercus*, etc., 1 female.

Conistra ligula (Esper, 1791) Montenegro: Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 male and 1 female. A new species for Montenegro, North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2024, 1 male.

Jodia croceago ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Tirana Region, Dajti Mt, Qafmolla Pass, 665 m, N41.3643, E019.9657, 04.IV.2019, *Quercus*, *Corylus*, *Acer* forest, 1 female; Gjirokaster, between Mal Čajup and Erind, 23.XI.2019; Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023; Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023; Prespa Lake, near Gllloboçeni Village, 05–06.XI.2023. Second report for Albania, up to now known only from Tirana (Misja, 1976).

Lithophane socia (Hufnagel, 1766) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male.

Lithophane merckii (Rambur, 1832) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2024, 1 male. Second report for Albania, previously known from Mali me

Gropë Mts, NW of Qafa e Selites (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020a); Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male (Fig. 284).

Lithophane lapidea (Hübner, [1808]) Albania: Prrrenjas-Pogradec, near Qafa Kotodeshit, 07.XI.2023, 1 male and 2 females; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 25.XI.2024, 1 male and 1 female; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 03.XI.2024, 1 female; Valandovo, near Rabrovo Village, 111 m, N41.2947, E022.5828, 23.XI.2024, *Paliurus*, vineyards, 1 male.

Xylena exsoleta (Linnaeus, 1758) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 10.III.2023, 1 male. Data from Rebel & Zerny (1931) for Žljeb are for the borderline of Montenegro/Serbia (Kosovo), not for Albania (Heinicke, 1965). New species for Albania.

Enargia paleacea (Esper, [1788]) Bulgaria: Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 male.

Ipimorpha subtusa ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 285). New species for Albania.

Fig. 286. *Dryobota labecula* ♂. B&H, Jasen 14.XI.2023.

Fig. 287. *Polymixis polymita* ♂. AI, Ploshtan 26.VIII.2023.

Cosmia confinis Herrich-Schäffer, 1849 Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Dryobota labecula (Esper, [1788]) Bosnia and Herzegovina: Leotar Mt, above Jasen Village, 14.XI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 286) and 1 female. New genus and new species for Bosnia and Herzegovina; Albania: Tepelene Region, Drino River, 27.XI.2024, 1 female; Benjë-Novoselë near Petran, 09.XI.2023, 1 female. Second locality for Albania, previously known only from Syri i Kaltër (Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019a).

Dichonia aeruginea (Hübner, [1808]) Montenegro: Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 male.

Dryobotodes monochroma (Esper, [1790]) Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 1 male. A new species for Montenegro; Albania: Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 1 male; Serbia: Golija Mts, Pleštin, Krnjača, 22.VI-II.2023, 3 males and 1 female; Bulgaria: above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024.

Dryobotodes servadeii Parenzan, 1982 Greece: between Florina and Edessa, 725 m, N40°39'29", E021°46'18", 02.IX.2010, S. Beshkov leg., 1 male; Bulgaria: Alibotush, above Goleshovo, 05.IX.2013, 1 male. This record is mentioned in Beshkov (2017) for Alibotush Mts but without locality; Sheynovets above Mezek, 07.X.2022, 1 male; E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 03.IX.2022, 1 male; Ibid, 05.X.2022, 7 males and 1 female, S. Beshkov & A. Nahirić-Beshkova leg.; Sakar, NW of Shtit, 12.X.2024, 1 female.

Dryobotodes carbonis (Wagner, 1931) Montenegro: Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 13.XI.2023, 1 male. A new species for Montenegro; Albania: Ksamil 28.XI.2024, 2 females; Bulgaria: Sakar, NW of Shtit, 12.X.2024, 1 female.

Fig. 288. *Polymixis serpentina* ♀. MNE, Povija 13.XI.2023.

Antityphe chi (Linnaeus, 1758) Bulgaria: Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 1 female.

Ammoconia senex (Geyer, [1828]) Montenegro: Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 male.

Trigonophora flammea (Esper, [1785]) Albania: Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 2 males; Ksamil 28.XI.2024, 1 female.

Dasypolia templi vecchumontium Ronkay & Varga, 1985 Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male; Ibid, 26.XI.2024, 1 male in negative temperature in the morning; Prespa Lake, near Gllloboçeni Village, 05–06.XI.2023, 1 male.

Polymixis polymita (Linnaeus, 1761) Albania: Kukës County, W. of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 1 male (Fig. 287). New species for Albania.

Polymixis serpentina (Treitschke, 1825) Montenegro: Ostroška Greda, near Povija, 13.XI.2023 (Fig. 288); Drume, Tuzi Municipality, 12.XI.2023, 1 male. Second report for Montenegro. Reported as new for the country from Morača River Valley near

Fig. 289. *Perigrapha i-cinctum slovenica* ♀. SRB, Veliki Čukar 06.IV.2024.

Fig. 290. *Anarta stigmosa atlantica* ♂. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

Bioče Village (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020a). Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male.

Polymixis culoti (Schawerda, 1921) Albania: Këlcyrës Gorge on Aoos River, 10.XI.2023, 1 male. This Eastern Mediterranean species is well represented on the Ionian Sea Coast. This locality is about 38 km in a straight line from the sea.

Mniotype solieri (Boisduval, 1840) Albania: Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 1 male.

Orthosia gracilis ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 female.

Orthosia opima (Hübner, [1809]) Serbia: Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 30.III.2024, 1 female.

Perigrapha i-cinctum slovenica Michielie, 1966 Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 06.IV.2024, 2 females (Fig. 289); Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 30.III.2024, 1 male; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 31.III.2024, 2 males.

Tholera cespitis ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 20.IX.2024. The report by Rebel & Zerny (1931) for Plav concerns Montenegro, not Albania (Heinicke, 1965). New species for Albania.

Cerapterys graminis (Linnaeus, 1758) Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 1 female. A new species for Montenegro.

Hadula odontites (Boisduval, 1929) Albania: Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 19.V.2023, 1 male.

Anarta mendax occidentalis Hacker, 1996 Albania: Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 2 males; Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 1 male; Mali me Gropa, 1466m, 19.VI.2023, 3 males; Tomori Mts, above Korita Village, 17.VI.2024, 1

Fig. 291. *Anarta stigmosa atlantica* ♂. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

male; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 28.V.2023 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 2 males; Bulgaria: Stargach Mt, above Ilinden Village, 14.VI.2023; E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024.

Anarta stigmosa (Christoph, 1887) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 4 males (Fig. 290) and 1 female (Fig. 291).

Cardepija hartigi (Parenzan, 1981) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 3 females (Figs 292–293). A new genus and new species for Albania.

Pachetra cherrug Rákosy & Wieser, 1997 Bulgaria: E Stara Planina Mts, above Sedlarevo, 566 m, 05.VI.2023, 12 males (Fig. 294) and 1 female. For Bulgaria, this species is reported from Kresna Gorge and illustrated in Varga et al. (2020). *Pachetra cherrug* is an endemic species of the Balkan Peninsula and, where it is present, it is abundant. In Kresna Gorge, however, which is the best explored area in Bulgaria, it is known from a single female specimen, collected there on 09–14.V.1989 (Varga et al., 2020). The range of *Pachetra cherrug* has a big disjunction – the Romanian part of Dobrogea, E Stara Planina in Bulgaria, and Kresna Gorge in SW Bulgaria.

Fig. 292. *Cardepija hartigi* ♂. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

Fig. 295. *Polia serratilinea kowatschevi* ♂. BG, Alibotush 22.VII.2023.

Fig. 293. *Cardepija hartigi* ♀. AL, Butrint 27.V.2023.

Fig. 296. *Polia serratilinea kowatschevi* ♀. BG, Alibotush 22.VII.2023.

Fig. 294. *Pachetra cherrug* ♂. BG, Sedlarevo 05.VI.2023.

Fig. 297. *Lacanobia thalassina* ♂. GR, Vigla 12.VI.2024.

Polia nebulosa (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male.

Polia serratilinea kowatschevi Drenowski, 1931 Bulgaria: Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 3 males (Fig. 295) and 2 females (Fig. 296), 1 female with pollinia. At Alibotush (= Slavyanka) Mt is the type locality of *Polia serratilinea kowatschevi*, which is an endemic for the Balkan Peninsula – Southern Bulgaria and Northern Greece.

Lacanobia thalassina (Hufnagel, 1766) Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 297). New species for Greece.

Lacanobia contigua ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets, 21.VII.2024. New species for Ossogovo Mts.

Lacanobia splendens (Hübner, [1808]) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 7 males (Fig. 298) and 4 females. New species for Albania.

Melanchra persicariae (Linnaeus, 1761) Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 male.

Sideridis lampra (Schawerda, 1913) Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 1 male.

Sideridis implexa (Hübner, [1809]) N Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 female.

Fig. 298. *Lacanobia splendens* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

Fig. 299. *Conisania renati meszarosi* ♀. BG, Radomir 24.V.2024.

Fig. 300. *Hecatera cappa* ♂. SRB, Bačevo 11.VIII.2024.

Conisania renati meszarosi Varga & Ronkay, 1991 Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 24.V.2024, 1 female (Fig. 299); Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 1 female. Very late flight period, usually this species flies in May–June. *Conisania renati meszarosi* is a Balkan endemic taxon, known from Western Bulgaria and Eastern Serbia.

Luteohadena luteago ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Qafa e Pashkasheshit above Iba, 21.V.2023, 1 male.

Hecatera cappa (Hübner, [1809]) Serbia: Vištin Kamen above Dimitrovgrad (= Caribrod), 11.VIII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 300); North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 female; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 17.VIII.2024, 1 male; Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024.

Enterpia laudeti laudeti (Boisduval, 1840) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 female; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 males; North Macedonia: Prilep, Pletvar Pass, 05.VII.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Golo Burdo Mt, above Radomir, 24.V.2024, 1 male; Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 4 males and 1 female; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 1 male.

Hadena magnolii (Boisduval, 1829) Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 2 males and 1 female, genitalia of 1 male checked.

Hadena compta ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 1 male. This is presumably the second generation of this species, which is usually univoltine, and a second generation is an exception in the southern part of the range.

Hadena adriana adriana (Schawerda, 1921) Albania: Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 1 male; Tomori Mts, above Korita Village, 17.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 4 males and 2 females; Prespa e vogel, near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 females.

Hadena gueneei (Staudinger, 1901) Albania: Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024, 3 males. In Serbia, *H. gueneei* is known from the same locality from the beginning of July (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020a) and from Trnava, Preševo Region, also from July (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2017).

Hadena vulcanica urumovi (Drenowski, 1931) Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 301) and 1 female; Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 1 female. This is the northernmost locality of this species on the Balkan Peninsula. This locality is very close to the border with Serbia, but *Hadena vulcanica urumovi* has not yet been reported from that country.

Fig. 301. *Hadena vulcanica urumovi* ♂. AL, Nivice 4.VII.2024.

Fig. 304. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* ♀. AL, Nivice 04.VII.2024, GP 1./10.II.2025.

Fig. 302. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* ♂. AL, Nivice 04.VII.2024, GP 4./10.II.2025.

Fig. 303. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* male genitalia with everted vesica AL, Nivice 04.VII.2024, GP 4./10.II.2025.

Fig. 305. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* female genitalia AL, Nivice 04.VII.2024, GP 1./10.II.2025.

Hadena wehrlii frequens Hacker, 1996 Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 302) and 1 female (Fig. 304), gen. prep. 4./10.II.2025 (Fig. 303), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal and gen. prep. 1./

10.II.2025 (Fig. 305), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal, apophyses posterior 8.3 mm. Wingspan of male 31.2 mm, this of female 31.2 mm; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 306), wingspan 30.2 mm, gen. prep. 3./10.II.2025 (Fig.

Fig. 306. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 18.VI.2024, GP 3./10.II.2025.

Fig. 309. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* ♂. NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024, GP 4./9.II.2025.

Fig. 307. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* male genitalia with everted vesica. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, GP 3./10.II.2025.

Fig. 310. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* male genitalia with everted vesica NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024 GP 4./9.II.2025.

Fig. 308. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* male genitalia with everted vesica GR, Vigla 12.VI.2024, GP 5./10.II.2025.

Fig. 311. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* ♀. NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024, GP 2./10.II.2025.

307), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male, wingspan 29.3 mm, gen. prep. 5./10.II.2025 (Fig. 308), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal; North Macedonia: Prilep, Pletvar Pass, 05.VII.2024, 1 male (Fig. 309), gen. prep. 4./09.II.2025 (Fig. 310), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on

Fig. 312. *Hadena wehrlii frequens* female genitalia NMK, Pletvar 05.VII.2024, GP 2./10.II.2025.

glass in euparal and 1 female (Fig. 311), gen. prep. 2./10.II.2025 (Fig. 312), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal, apophyses posterior 8.5 mm. Wingspan of male 27.5 mm; of female – 30.5 mm.

Hadena persimilis balcanica Hacker, 1996
Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 female (Fig. 313), gen. prep. 2./15.II.2025 (Fig. 314), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal. Length of apophyses posterior – 9.0 mm. Wingspan – 29.2 mm.

Hadena persimilis persimilis Hacker, 1996
Bulgaria: S Pirin Mts, between Karlanovo and Sugarevo villages, 670 m, 16.VII.2004, *Quercus* forest and meadows on sandy slopes, S. Beshkov, M. & B. Beshkovi leg. at 160 W MVL, 18 W black tube and light trap, 3 males and 1 female, gen. prep. 2./26. I.2006, S. Beshkov, female genitalia in Euparal;

Fig. 313. *Hadena persimilis balcanica* ♀. AL, Plespa e vogel, Tren 13.VI.2024, GP 2./15.II.2025.

Fig. 314. *Hadena persimilis balcanica* female genitalia with 8th segment AL, Plespa e vogel, Tren 13.VI.2024, GP 2./15.II.2025.

Eastern Rhodopi Mts, between Zvanarka and Pobeda, suburb of Ovchari Village, Kroumovgrad district, 347 m, N41°26'26", E025°38'02", 16.VII.2007, slopes with grass vegetation, *Paliurus*, marble rocks, 2 males; Ibid, 19.VII.2009, 2 males (Fig. 315), wing span 31.2 mm; Eastern Rhodopi Mts, 5 km north of Gugutka Village, Ivaylovgrad District, 320 m, N41°26'58.7", E025°56'50.6", 19.VII.2006, near river with ruderal, S. Beshkov & M. Marinov leg. at daytime, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 female (Fig. 316), wing span 30.3 mm, Gen. prep. 1./

Fig. 315. *Hadena persimilis persimilis* ♂. BG, Zvanarka-Pobeda 16.VII.2007.

Fig. 316. *Hadena persimilis persimilis* ♀. BG, Shtit, 31.V.2024 GP 1./15.II.2025.

15/II.2025 (Fig. 317), S. Beshkov, female genitalia on glass in euparal. Length of the apophyses anterior = 8.1 mm; Sakar Mt, Matochina Village, Bukelon Castle, 206 m, N41°51'15", E026°32'48", 19.VIII.2005, steppe area with *Paliurus* on limestone rocky hill, 2 males. *Hadena persimilis* is mentioned for Matochina in Beshkov & Nahirić (2020a), but without the further data given here.

In the mountain area of the Central Balkan Peninsula, around the corner of North Macedonia, Albania and Greece, *Hadena wehrlii frequens*, *Hadena persimilis balcanica*, *Hadena luteocincta* (Rambur, 1834), and *Hadena perpetua* Hacker, 1996 are sometimes sympatric, synchronic, and syntopic. It is often hard to decide on how to split and identify these very similar taxa, especially the male individuals of *Hadena wehrlii frequens*, *Hadena persimilis balcanica* and *Hadena luteocincta*, as well as the females of *Hadena wehrlii frequens* and *Hadena persimilis balcanica* (*luteocincta* group). The identification above for the *luteocincta* group is provisional and not believed to be exactly correct.

Hadena filograna (Esper, [1788]) Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male;

Fig. 317. *Hadena persimilis persimilis* female genitalia. BG, Shtit, 31.V.2024 GP 1./15.II.2025.

Fig. 318. *Hadena filograna* ♂. SRB, Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024.

Serbia: Veliki Čukar, 10.VI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 318) and 2 females.

Fig. 319. *Hadena caesia xanthophoba* ♀. AL, Tomori 16.VI.2024.

Fig. 321. *Hadena drenowskii drenowskii* ♀. BG, Komshtitsa 09.VIII.2021.

Fig. 320. *Hadena clara macedonica* ♂. AL, Bregas 14.V.2024.

Fig. 322. *Hadena drenowskii drenowskii* ♂. BG, Alibotush below Livada, 22.VII.2023.

Hadena caesia xanthophoba (Schawerda, 1922) Albania: Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male; Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 3 males and 1 female (Fig. 319); Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 2 males.

Hadena caesia ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) ssp? Greece: Vigla, between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked. This specimen differs from the *Hadena caesia xanthophoba* illustrated here, and we cannot at present decide the status of this population.

Hadena clara macedonica Boursin, 1959 Albania: Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 320). In Albania known only from Mali me Gropa, Central part S. of plateau, 1501 m (Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021). Second locality for Albania. *Hadena clara macedonica* is a Balkan endemic taxon, known from Northern Macedonia, Greece and Albania.

Hadena drenowskii drenowskii (Rebel, 1930) Albania: Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 2

males. This is the earliest recorded flight period of this species in the Balkans, or even at all; Serbia: Bela Palanka, Šljivovički Vis Mt, above Šljivovik Village, 1043 m, N43.1519, E022.3848, 13.VIII.2021, limestone steppe-like grasslands with *Artemisia alba*, 1 male; Bulgaria: Godech Municipality, above Komshtitsa Village, 1163 m, N43.1017, E023.0096, 09.VIII.2021, slopes with *Artemisia alba*, *Pinus nigra*, dry rocky grasslands, 1 female (Fig. 321). The last two sites are the most northern localities of the nominotypical *Hadena drenowskii drenowskii* as the population in Ukraine belongs to *Hadena drenowskii lapidea* Klyuchko & Hacker, 1996; Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 9 males and 3 females; Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 2 males (Fig. 322). Alibotush in Bulgaria is the type locality of *Hadena drenowskii*. The nominotypical *Hadena drenowskii* is a Balkan endemic taxon, known from Bulgaria, Greece, Northern Macedonia, Serbia and Albania.

Hadena syriaca podolica (Kremky, 1937) Albania: Himara, above Kudhes, 25.V.2023, 1 male

Fig. 323. *Hadena tephroleuca tephroleuca* ♂. AL, Bregas, 14.VI.2024.

Fig. 325. *Mythimna anderreggii pseudocomma* ♂. GR, Vigla 12.VI.2024.

Fig. 324. *Mythimna pudorina* ♂. AL, Prespa e vogel, Tren, 13.VI.2024.

and 4 females; Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 28.V.2023, 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 female; Bulgaria: Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male; Pirin, Hrasna, 30.VI.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Alibotush Mts, below Livada, above Goleshovo Village, 1560 m, N41°24'58", E023°36'51", 18.VI.2013, mountain meadows in coniferous forest on limestone area, S. Beshkov, B. Zlatkov, O. Sivilov leg., 1 male; Sakar Mt, below Vishegrad, near Kostur, 04.VI.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, 17.V.2024, 1 male; NW above Glushnik Village, 02.VI.2023, 1 female; Yambol Region, Bakadzhik Hill, below the TV Tower above Turnava Village, 471 m, N42.4507, E026.6854, 03.VI.2023, slopes with *Paliurus*, *Quercus*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Astracantha*, 1 male and 1 female.

Hadena silenes (Hübner, [1822]) Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Oreshnik, 06.V.2024, 3 males.

Hadena tephroleuca tephroleuca (Boisduval, 1833) Albania: Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 323).

Mythimna pudorina ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 2 males (Fig. 324). New species for Albania.

Mythimna impura (Hübner, [1822]) Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 1 female. Reported as a new for Montenegro from Tara Canyon, Tepca (Beshkov, 2009b). Second report for Montenegro. Bulgaria: Ossogovo Mts, below Kunets, 21.VII.2024, 1 male.

Mythimna straminea (Treitschke, 1825) Albania: Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 female; Ibid, 20.IX.2024, 1 male and 1 female; Bulgaria: Novo Leski, 13.VI.2023, 1 male; Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female; NW above Glushnik Village, 02.VI.2023, 1 male.

Mythimna anderreggii pseudocomma Rebel & Zerny, 1931 Albania: Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male; Greece: Vigla between Florina and Pisoderi, 12.VI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 325); Bulgaria: Rila Mts, Blagoevgrad Region, near Makedonia Chalet, 2191 m, N42.0503, E023.4322, 24.VII.2023, subalpine slopes with *Pinus mugo*, *Chamaecytisus absinthioides*, *Verbascum*, 1 male.

Mythimna alopecuri (Boisduval, 1840) Serbia: Bela Palanka, above Moklište, 07.IV.2024, 3 males, genitalia checked; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male, genitalia checked; Golo Burdo, Golata Mogila, 13.IV.2024, 1 male, genitalia checked; above Bosnek, 24.VIII.2024.

Mythimna prominens (Walker, 1856) Albania: Cape of Rodon, 23.V.2023, 1 male; Butrint, 27.V.2023, 3 males (Fig. 326).

Mythimna languida (Walker, 1858) Albania: Ksamil 28.XI.2024, 1 male (Fig. 327); Fier, above Radostinë Village, 11.XI.2023, 1 female.

Fig. 326. *Mythimna prominens* ♂. AL, Cape of Rodon, 23.V.2023.

Fig. 328. *Leucania obsoleta* ♂. AL, Kosan 02.VII.2024l.

Fig. 327. *Mythimna languida* ♂. AL, Ksamil 28.XI.2024.

Fig. 329. *Leucania putrescens* male genitalia with everted vesica. AL, Lin 24.IX.2024, GP 1./30.I.2025.

Mythimna congrua (Hübner, [1817]) Albania: Cape of Rodon, 23.V.2023, 1 female; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Danube Plain, Golubačka peščara, Vinci vicinity, Prokop, 96 m, N44.70782, E021.58797, 06.VI.2020, sandy soil area. Second report for Serbia. *Mythimna congrua* was recently published as a new for Serbia from Novi Sad, Zlotski kanjon near Bor, “Gornje Podunavlje” Natural Reserve and “Deliblatski pesak” Natural Reserve (Stojanović et al., 2024).

Mythimna riparia (Rambur, 1829) Albania: Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 2 males; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 20.IX.2024, 1 male; North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Struma Valley – S. Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlahi, 25.V.2024, 1 female; Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 1 male; E. Rhodopi, Egrek, 05.VI.2024, 2 males and 1 female; Krichim, Izgoryaloto Gyune, 23.IX.2023, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 2 males; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 male;

Sakar, near Mramor Village, 03.VI.2024, 2 males and 1 female; Sakar, above Karabashka Reka between Sladun and Varnik, 02.VI.2024, 1 female.

Leucania obsoleta (Hübner, 1803) Albania: Shkodra Lake, Kosan, 02.VII.2024, 2 males (Fig. 328); Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 20.V.2023, 1 male; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male.

Leucania putrescens (Hübner, [1824]) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 2 males; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 male, gen. prep. 1./30.I.2025 (Fig. 329), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal.

Fig. 330. *Dichagyris musiva* ♂. MNE, Ski Center above Kolašin 24.VIII.2023.

Fig. 332. *Euxoa diaphora* ♂. BG, Pobitite Kamani 7.IX.2022.

Fig. 331. *Euxoa distinguenda distincta* ♂. AL, Ploshtan 26.VIII.2023.

Leucania herrichii Herrich-Schäffer, [1849] Greece: between Florina and Edessa, 725 m, N40°39'29", E021°46'18", 02.IX.2010, maquis, S. Beshkov leg., 1 male and 1 female at light trap; Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodopi Mts, "Meandrite na Byala Reka" near Meden Bouk Village, Ivaylovgrad district, 130 m, N41°22'58", E026°01'21", 16.IX.2006, S. Beshkov & B. Zlatkov leg.

Dichagyris musiva (Hübner, [1803]) Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 5 males (Fig. 330). A new species for Montenegro; Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 6 males and 1 female. In Serbia known from Karaula and Vasilin Vrh (Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2020). Second report for Serbia; Bulgaria: W. Rhodopi Mts, above Trigrad Gorge, 02.IX.2022, 1 male; Strandzha "Pirena" above Kostî, 10.VII.2024, 1 male. This is the lowest locality on the Balkans and not a typical habitat for this montane species.

Dichagyris candelisequa ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Suva Planina, Divna Gorica, 09.VIII.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Dichagyris melanura (Kollar, 1846) North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Dichagyris renigera (Hübner, [1808]) Albania: Tepelene, above Nivice Village, 04.VII.2024, 1 male aberrant; Maja e Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Gramsh Region, Valamara Mts, below Liqueni i Zi, 1744 m, N40.7475, E020.4295, 22.VII.2022, mountain meadows above *Fagus* forest, 1 female; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 18.VI.2024, 1 male; Pogradec, Guri i Kamjes, 05.VI.2022, 1 male; Galičica Mts, above Bregas, 14.VI.2024, 1 female; Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female.

Euxoa conspicua (Hübner, [1827]) = *agricola* (Boisduval, 1829) North Macedonia: Vardar Valley, Demir Kapija Gorge, 97 m, N41°24'28", E022°16'11", 21.VI.1995, one specimen at 125W MVL with 25W blacklight lamp, S. Beshkov, S. Abadjiev & Og. Iliev leg.; Bulgaria: Belassitsa Mts, "Varshiloto" below Malak Kongour Top, 1600 m, 14.VII.2002, subalpine meadow with *Juniperus* and *Vaccinium* above *Fagus* forest, S. Beshkov, J. Nowacki & M. Bunalski leg. at 160 W MVL with 18 W black tube and light trap, 1 male.

Euxoa distinguenda distincta Staudinger, 1892 Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 4 males; Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 4 males (Fig. 331); Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 03.IX.2022, 2 males; Ibid, 05.X.2022, S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova leg., 2 males.

Euxoa diaphora Boursin, 1928 Bulgaria: Bulgaria: Northern Black Sea Coast, the main group of "Pobitite Kamani", Varna Region, 106 m, N43.2234, E027.7068, 07.IX.2022, sandy area with grass vegetation, S. Beshkov, R. Wasala & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova leg. (Fig. 332).

Fig. 333. *Euxoa pareruta* ♂. BG, Kresna-Vlahi 03.VI.2022.

Fig. 336. *Euxoa pareruta* everted vesica. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023, GP 1./24.II.2025.

Fig. 334. *Euxoa pareruta* ♀. BG, Kresna-Vlahi 03.VI.2022.

Fig. 337. *Euxoa pareruta* everted vesica. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023, GP 1./24.II.2025.

Fig. 335. *Euxoa pareruta* male genitalia. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023, GP 1./24.II.2025.

Fig. 338. *Euxoa pareruta* male genitalia. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023, GP 2./24.II.2025.

Euxoa pareruta Fibiger, Gyulai, Zilli, Yela & Ronkay, 2010 SW Bulgaria: Struma River Valley – S Pirin Mts, above Kresna Town from the road to Vlahi Village, 529 m, N41.73034, E023.2003, 03.VI.2022, slopes with *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. oxycedrus*, *Paliurus*, *Quercus*, etc. 21 males (Fig. 333) and 11 females (Fig. 334); Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlahi,

25.V.2024, 5 males and 1 female; Marino Pole, 16.VI.2023, 8 males and 7 females, gen. preps 1./24.II.2025 (Figs 335–337) and 2./24.II.2025 (Figs 338–340), S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal. The male genitalia, particularly the shape of the valvae, are very variable even in specimens from one series.

Fig. 339. *Euxoa pareruta* everted vesica. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023, GP 2./24.II.2025.

Fig. 340. *Euxoa pareruta* everted vesica. BG, Marino Pole 16.VI.2023, GP 2./24.II.2025.

Euxoa cos cos (Hübner, [1824]) Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male.

Euxoa cos crimaea A. Bang-Haas, 1906 Bulgaria: Silvercoast, “Bukvite” above Balchik, 06.IX.2022, 16 males (Figs 341–342) and 1 female; Ibid, 19.VIII.2021, S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova leg., 1 male (Fig. 343). We use the name *crimaea* A. Bang-Haas for the very characteristic population at the Silvercoast for the reasons explained here under *Caradrina pertinax argentea*.

Euxoa aquilina ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Bulgaria: Pirin, Hrasna, 30.VI.2023, 2 males (Fig. 344).

Euxoa hastifera (Donzel, 1847) Albania: Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 4 males (Fig. 345); Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024. New species for Albania; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male.

Euxoa decora macedonica Thurner, 1936 Montenegro: Ski Centre above Kolašin, 24.VIII.2023, 6 males and 1 female.

Fig. 341. *Euxoa cos crimaea* ♂. BG, Balchik, Bukvite 06.IX.2022.

Fig. 342. *Euxoa cos crimaea* ♂. BG, Balchik, Bukvite 06.IX.2022.

Fig. 343. *Euxoa cos crimaea* ♂. BG, Balchik, Bukvite 19.VIII.2021.

Fig. 344. *Euxoa aquilina* ♂. BG, Hrasna 30.VI.2023.

Fig. 345. *Euxoa hastifera* ♂. AL, Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023.

Fig. 346. *Agrotis catalaunensis* ♂. AL, Ardenica 06.V.2022.

Agrotis catalaunensis (Millière, 1868) Albania: Lushnja, above Ardenica, 06.V.2022, 2 males (Fig. 346); Çorovoda, Osumi river canyon, opposite Kalanjas Village, 419 m, N40.4846, E020.2362, 05.V.2022, maquis with *Phyllirea*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Quercus ilex*, *Quercus* sp., *Palliurus*, *Cotinus coggigria*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, etc., 3 males; Devoli Gorge, near Bratilo, 04.V.2022, 2 males.

Agrotis spinifera (Hübner, [1808]) = *biconica* Kollar, 1844 Bulgaria: Sakar, Shtit, 01.VI.2024, 1 male; Sakar, above Sladun Village, 02.V.2024, 1 male.

Ochropleura leucogaster (Freyer, [1831]) Albania: Butrint, 27.V.2023, 1 male and 2 females; Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023, 1 female; Prespa e vogel near Tren, 13.VI.2024, 1 male; Serbia: Veliki čukar, 06.IV.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Struma Valley – S Pirin Mts, Kresna – Vlazi, 25.V.2024, 1 male; Sakar, Shtit, Mogilata, 31.V.2024, 1 female.

Epipsilia grisescens (Fabricius, 1794) Montenegro: Durmitor Mts, Veliki Štuoc, 06.VIII.2015. 2 males.

Rhyacia simulans (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 3 males, genitalia of 1

Fig. 347. *Rhyacia arenacea* male genitalia with everted vesica. BG, Chepan 1167 m, 12.VII.2023, GP 2./18. IV.2024.

Fig. 348. *Rhyacia nyctymeridis stavroitiacus* ♀. AL, Tomori 26.VI.2024.

male checked, in glycerol in a microvial; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 2 females and 1 male, genitalia of one checked, in glycerol in microvial; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 female; Bulgaria: Sakar Mt, below Vishegrad, near Kostur, 04.VI.2024, 1 male, genitalia with everted vesica in a microvial in glycerol.

Rhyacia arenacea (Hampson, 1907) Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 22.VII.2023, 1 male, gen. prep. 2./18.IV.2024, S. Beshkov, male genitalia with everted vesica on glass in euparal (Fig. 347). This locality close to the border with Serbia suggests that *R. arenacea* may occur in Serbia as well.

Rhyacia nyctymeridis stavroitiacus Toulechkoff, 1951 Albania: Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female (Fig. 348). Known

Fig. 349. *Chersotis multangula* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

Fig. 351. *Standfussiana lucernea illyrica* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

Fig. 350. *Chersotis elegans* ♂. AL, Terbunit 25.VIII.2023.

Fig. 352. *Standfussiana lucernea illyrica* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 23.VI.2023.

from this area but from a higher altitude in July and August (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019; Beshkov et al. 2020). *Rhyacia nyctymeridis stavroitiacus* is a Balkan endemic taxon, known from Greece and Albania only.

Chersotis multangula (Hübner, [1803]) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 349), genitalia checked, in microvial in glycerol and 1 female; Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 1 male.

Chersotis elegans (Eversmann, 1837) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 2 males (Fig. 350); Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 2 males and 1 female, genitalia of one male checked, in microvial in glycerol.

Chersotis fimbriola thurneri Varga, Gyulai, Ronkay, L. & Ronkay, G., 2013 (= *fimbriola forsteri* Thurner, 1964, nom. praeocc.) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 2 males and 1 female; Ibid, 18.VI.2024, 14 males and 5 females.

Chersotis fimbriola (Esper, [1803]) ssp. North Macedonia: Dračev Dol, below Rebre, 11.VI.2024, 5

males and 3 females. This is a low-elevation population, and it differs significantly in size and colouration from *Chersotis fimbriola thurneri*. A specimen from this population, but from a different locality (Demirkapija), is illustrated in Koren et al. (2021) together with a specimen of *Chersotis fimbriola thurneri*. The genetic data, however, show no significant differences between the populations (Koren et al. 2021).

Chersotis cuprea ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 male.

Standfussiana lucernea illyrica (Rebel & Zerny, 1931) Albania: Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 2 males (Figs 351–352) genitalia of 1 male checked, in microvial in glycerol.

Noctua tirrenica Biebinger, Speidel & Hanigk, 1983 Bulgaria: Rila, above Karagyol reservoir below Kalin Peak, 25.VII.2023, 1 female, genitalia checked. This seems to be the highest record of this species anywhere. This specimen in such an unusual habitat is

Fig. 353. *Noctua janthe* ♂. AL, Trebunit 25.VIII.2023.

Fig. 355. *Xestia castanea michaeli* ♂. AL, Lin 24.IX.2024.

Fig. 354. *Noctua janthe* ♂. AL, Maja Ahishtes Geges 18.VI.2024.

Fig. 356. *Xestia castanea michaeli* ♂. BG, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023.

probably a result of migration or passive thermal transportation. The thesis for the possible migration of *Noctua tirrenica* is expressed by Rezbanyai-Reser & Hächler (2013), who reported a specimen from 2000 m a.s.l. in the Alps.

Noctua orbona (Hufnagel, 1766) Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male.

Noctua janthe (Borkhausen, 1792) Albania: Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 male (Fig. 353); Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male (Fig. 354); Serbia: Golija Mts, Plešin, Krnjača, 22.VIII.2023, 1 male; Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 21.VIII.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Ibid 07.VIII.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 female.

Noctua tertia von Mentzer, Moberg & Fibiger, 1991 Serbia: Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885m, 21.VIII.2023, 1 male and 1 female.

Divaena haywardi (Tams, 1926) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male; Maja e

Manjolave, 20.VI.2023, 2 males and 1 female; Puke, Terbunit Mts, 25.VIII.2023, 1 female; Tomori Mts, Tomori i Madh Village, 15.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female; Kukës County, W of Ploshtan, 26.VIII.2023; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 3 males; Ibid, 18.VI.2024, 1 male and 1 female; Serbia: above Veliki čukar, 982 m, 03.VII.2021, 1 male; Veliki Čukar, 04.VII.2021, 1 female; Ibid, 06.IV.2024, 6 males and 8 females; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 female; Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 2 males and 3 females; Alibotush, below Livada, 22.VII.2023, 1 female; Strandzha “Pirena” above Kosti, 10.VII.2024.

Xestia castanea michaeli Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024 Albania: Korçë, Monastir Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 1 male and 1 female; Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 1 male; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 1 male (Fig. 355); Mt Kuq, below Qarrit Pass, 21.IX.2024, 3 males and 1 female; Serbia: Suva Planina above Bela Palanka, 06.IX.2024, 3 males;

Fig. 357. *Eugnorisma pontica* ♀. AL, Vithkuq 22.IX.2024.

Fig. 358. *Eugnorisma pontica* ♂. SRB, Smilovci 07.IX.2024.

Fig. 359. *Spaelotis senna contorta* ♂. Suva Planina above Bela Palanka 1071 m 30.VI.2021.

Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 07.IX.2024, 4 males; Bulgaria: Trun, Krivonoska Mogila near Rebro, 02.IX.2023, 1 male, dark form (Fig. 356).

Xestia cohaesa (Herrich-Schäffer, [1849]) Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 2 males and 1 female; Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 2 males; Ohrid Lake, Lin Peninsula, 24.IX.2024, 2 males and 2 females; Bulgaria: E. Rhodopi Mts, Ivaylovgrad, Likana, 05.X.2022, 2 males and 1 female; Sakar Mt, above Topolovgrad,

13.X.2024, 1 male; Sakar, NW of Shtit, 12.X.2024, 1 male; Sakar, SE below Mihalich Village, 11.X.2024, 1 male and 2 females.

Xestia ashworthii gergelypeteri Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024 Montenegro: Pirlitor, near Vrela, 01.VII.2024, 2 males. The subspecific status of the Balkan population of *Xestia ashworthii* (Doubleday, 1855) is not clarified yet. In Montenegro, we identified it as belonging to the ssp. *gergelypeteri* Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024. From Eastern Serbia (Suva Planina), three specimens are illustrated in colour and identified as *Xestia ashworthii candelarum* (Staudinger, 1871) (Beshkov et al., 2024).

Eugnorisma pontica (Staudinger, 1892) Albania: Korçë, Monastery Peter & Pavel above Vithkuq, 22.IX.2024, 2 males and 3 females (Fig. 357). New species for Albania; Serbia: Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 07.IX.2024, 4 males (Fig. 358) and 1 female. New species for Serbia.

Eugraphe sigma ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 female. According to Vasić (2002) and Stojanović & Curčić (2011), *Eugraphe sigma* is known only from Northern (Vojvodina) and Eastern Serbia (Stol, Timočka Krajina).

Spaelotis senna contorta (Rebel & Zerny, 1931) Albania: Llogara, 1240 m, 21.VI.2023, 1 male; Mali me Gropa, 1466 m, 19.VI.2023, 1 male and 1 female; Tomori Mts, below Abaz Ali Top, 16.VI.2024, 1 female; Maja Ahishtes Geges, 23.VI.2023, 1 male; Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes, 23.IX.2024, 1 female; Serbia: Četanica Mts, near Karaula, 30.VI.2024, 1 female; Rtanj Mt, Vrtače above Mužinac, 885 m, 07.VIII.2024, 1 male; Suva Planina, above Bela Palanka Town, 1071 m, N43.1983, E022.2551, 30.VI.2021, ecotone of *Fagus forest* with *Corylus colurna* and road with *Artemisia alba* on limestone background, 2 males (Fig. 359); Šljivovički Vis, 21.VI.2017, 2 males and 1 female; Vidlič Mt, Jankov Dol above Smilovci, 07.IX.2024, 1 male; Bulgaria: Chepan, Petrovski Krust, 12.VII.2023, 2 males and 2 females.

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